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Report on MIRRI-User survey

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1. INTRODUCTION

Objectives of the survey:

- Gather information on current and potential users of mBRCs
- Define users' general needs and expectations regarding preservation of genetic resources¹ (GR), supply of GR of related data and services
- Identify the problems encountered by users in depositing their GR and/or in obtaining GR, related data or services
- Assess potential gaps in the offer of GR, data or related services offered by public culture collections (CCs)
- Assess the awareness of and compliance to the Convention on Biological Diversity and legal issues related to the Access to GR and the Sharing of Benefits resulting from their (commercial) use

Target groups of the survey:

- The **current users** of GR and/or associated data and services.
- The **potential users** of GR and/or associated data and services.

¹Culturable organisms (e.g. micro-organisms, plant, animal and human cells), replicable parts of these (e.g. genomes, plasmids, viruses, cDNAs), viable but not yet culturable organisms, cells and tissues.
Description taken from the OECD consensus report "*Biological Resource Centres: underpinning the future of life sciences and biotechnology*" (OECD, 2001)

2. METHODOLOGY

An online survey consisting of 41 questions was set up in English (Annex 1). To assist respondents, translated PDF versions of the questionnaire were also made available online in Spanish, Italian, French and Russian, but responses were collected in English only. Respondents participating in the survey were given the choice whether or not to answer the questionnaire anonymously, but they had to agree with the terms laid down in the MIRRI Statement on Use, Access and Protection of Collected data (Annex 2).

To reach the respondents, the MIRRI partners and collaborating parties (34 CCs from 17 countries, Annex 3), were asked to provide the link to the online questionnaire to their customers of at least the past seven years. In addition, 69 national scientific associations in 31 European countries (Annex 4) and 7 international scientific associations (Annex 5) were asked to request their members to respond to the online survey. The European Federation of Biotechnology (EFB) was also involved to reach potential users by including a link on the EFB homepage to the MIRRI webpage referring to the online questionnaire.

The online questionnaire was initially accessible for 42 days (April 9th until June 21st, 2013) during which **1146 valid responses** were received, i.e. the respondent answered a minimal number of questions. The questionnaire was then reopened (January 21st until June 27th) together with the launch of the Innovative Services survey. **48 additional responses** from this second round brought the total number of **valid responses to 1194**. The survey was fully completed by 870 respondents (72.8%), whereas 324 of the replies (27.1%) were incomplete but valid and therefore taken into account for the analysis. Chapter 3 of this document presents a summary of the received responses.

No data was gathered on the numbers of users reached by each distribution channel (mailings to current CC users or members of microbiological associations, or the EFB or MIRRI website). Consequently, a total response rate and response rate per distribution channel could not be calculated.

The general information section of the questionnaire (Annex 1), identifying the user, was skipped by 894 respondents (74.9 %) and classified as anonymous replies, whereas 300 respondents (24.6 %) provided personal contact details and information on their function, organization, and laboratory unit. Hence, this latter group of users, 233 from the non-profit sector and 67 from the profit sector, can be contacted again for additional information on their laboratory unit's needs and expectations, and to represent the user community in the future development processes of MIRRI.

3. RESULTS

*The percentages given in this summary report are calculated based on the number of respondents **per question** and not the total number of respondents of the survey, unless stated otherwise.*

It is important to realize that respondents were given the opportunity to skip questions during the questionnaire, which explains the different total number of respondents for different questions.

If respondents were allowed to select several options that apply, this is indicated as “multiple answers”.

3.1. Respondent profiles

3.1.1. Country of origin (Q5)

All respondents represented 61 different countries. The majority of these respondents (81%) originated from 29 European countries (including the Russian Federation), while 29% of the responses came from 32 countries from outside Europe.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the 967 respondents from the 29 **European countries** (including the Russian Federation). Of all respondents, 870 (72.9 %) originated from the host countries of one or more CCs that participate in the MIRRI preparatory phase project as a full partner (bold) or as a collaborating party, and 95 (7.9 %) originated from thirteen other European countries without MIRRI partners or collaborating parties.

Table 1. Number of respondents and list of CCs collaborating in MIRRI¹ from European countries and the Russian Federation (¹CCs that are full partners in MIRRI are in bold. See Annex 3 for full name and details of CCs collaborating in the MIRRI preparatory phase.)

Country	Number of respondents	% of total respondents	List of CCs collaborating in the MIRRI preparatory phase project
Spain	270	22.6	CECT
Germany	130	10.9	DSMZ, SAG
Italy	87	7.2	MUT, ICLC, ITEM, DBVPG
Portugal	82	6.9	MUM, PYCC
France	62	5.2	CIP-CRBIP, CIRM-BIA, CIRM-BP, CIRM-CF, CIRM-CFBP, CIRM-Levures
UK	52	4.4	CABI, NCIMB
The Netherlands	46	3.8	CBS
Belgium	43	3.6	BCCM-LMG, BCCM-IHEM, BCCM-LMBP, BCCM-MUCL
Czech Republic	31	2.6	CCF
Switzerland	24	2.0	-
Sweden	20	1.7	CCUG
Russian Federation	17	1.4	VKM, IEGM
Denmark	18	1.5	-
Austria	15	1.3	-
Ireland	10	0.8	-
Finland	8	0.7	VTTCC
Hungary	7	0.6	NCAIM
Turkey	7	0.6	-
Poland	7	0.6	IAFB, PCM
Norway	6	0.5	-
Greece	6	0.5	ACA-DC, ATHUM
Slovakia	4	0.3	CCY
Croatia	4	0.3	-
Bulgaria	3	0.3	-
Slovenia	3	0.3	-
Romania	2	0.2	-
Liechtenstein	1	0.1	-
Luxembourg	1	0.1	-
Serbia	1	0.1	-
Latvia	0	0.0	MSCL
Responses from 29 countries	967	81.0	

Table 2 shows the distribution of the 224 respondents (19 %) from 32 **countries outside Europe**: 98 from Asia, 91 from the Americas, 14 from Africa, and 11 from Australia and Oceania.

Table 2. Number of respondents from countries outside Europe

Non-European countries	Number of respondents	% of total respondents	Region or continent
United States	64	5.4	North-America
China	30	2.5	Asia
India	26	2.2	Asia
Japan	13	1.1	Asia
Canada	12	1.0	North-America
Korea	11	0.9	Asia
Australia	9	0.8	Australia & Oceania
South Africa	9	0.8	Africa
Israel	7	0.6	Asia
Brazil	5	0.4	South-America
Mexico	5	0.4	South-America
Singapore	5	0.4	Asia
New Zealand	3	0.3	Australia & Oceania
Thailand	3	0.3	Asia
Argentina	2	0.2	South-America
Chile	2	0.2	South-America
Egypt	2	0.2	Africa
Saudi Arabia	2	0.2	Asia
Tunisia	2	0.2	Africa
Algeria	1	0.1	Africa
Bolivia	1	0.1	South-America
Costa Rica	1	0.1	South-America
Côte d'Ivoire	1	0.1	Africa
Indonesia	1	0.1	Asia
Iraq	1	0.1	Asia
Kuwait	1	0.1	Asia
Malaysia	1	0.1	Asia
Taiwan	1	0.1	Asia
Vietnam	1	0.1	Asia
Iran	1	0.1	Asia
United Arab Emirates	1	0.1	Asia
Responses from 32 countries	224	19	

3.1.2. Organization type (Q8-10)

The **non-profit** sector accounted for **910 respondents** (76.3 %), of which the majority were academics (60.3 %) or from research institutes (33.7 %), whether or not in combination with (an) other type(s) (Table 3) while control or Reference analyses laboratories (7.3 %), Hospitals (4.7 %), Schools (1.3 %) and Foundations (1.3 %) were less represented. Other organization types mentioned by the respondents were e.g. governmental and international research institutes, associations, and biological resource, education or technical centres.

The **profit** sector accounted for **282 respondents** (23.7 %), of which the majority represented small to medium size enterprises, corresponding to 10.0 % of all respondents. Large enterprises and micro-enterprises represented 8.4 % and 5.1 % of all respondents, respectively.

Table 3. Number of respondents per organization type (non-profit sector) or per size (profit sector)
(multiple answers allowed)

Sector	Organization type(s) ¹ (non-profit) or size of the enterprise (profit)	Number of respondents	% within sector	% of all respondents (N = 1189)
Non-profit Answered: 907	University	546	60.3	45.9
	Research Institute	305	33.7	25.7
	Control or Reference analyses lab	66	7.3	5.6
	Hospital	43	4.7	3.6
	Other	20	2.2	1.7
	School	12	1.3	1.0
	Foundation	12	1.3	1.0
Profit Answered: 282	Small to Medium size enterprise (10-250 employees)	119	42.2	10.0
	Large enterprise (>250 employees)	101	35.8	8.5
	Micro-enterprise (< 10 employees)	62	22.0	5.2

3.1.3. Field of Activity of the respondents (Q11: 1170 replies)

When asked for their respective field of activity, respondents were allowed to check multiple answers and most of the respondents made use of this option. Overall, the top five fields of activity of the respondents was (Figure 1):

1. Research & education (56.8 %)
2. Food & feed (19.9 %)
3. Environment (18.5 %)
4. Pharma & medical (16.0 %)
5. Agronomy (12.2 %)

A clear difference in the fields of activity was observed between non-profit and profit respondents.

Within the **non-profit** user group, **research & education** (67.2 %) was the major field of activity, followed by **environment** (19.1 %) and **food & feed** (15.3 %). The veterinary and chemical fields were least represented with 5.1 % and 3.9 % of non-profit users, respectively. Other activities mentioned by the non-profit respondents included e.g. (bio)engineering, biotechnology, epidemiology, genetics, water control, and statistics.

Within the **profit** user group, activities were **more diverse**, but the most represented fields were **food & feed** (34.9 %) and **pharma & medical** (32.4 %). Other categories mentioned by the profit respondents were e.g. cosmetics, nanotechnology, production, bio-deterioration, biotechnology, mining and minerals, gas and oil, and textile (Annex 6 gives an overview of all responses).

3.1.4. Qualification level of user laboratory personnel (Q14-15)

In **non-profit** laboratory units, the GR are handled by staff with a university or a PhD degree (Figure 2). In **profit** laboratory units, the GR are handled mostly by staff with a University degree (Figure 2) or Laboratory technicians (Figure 2). In about half of laboratory units, both **non-profit** and **profit**, the main qualification level of the staff was a university degree (Figure 3).

For 37.6 % of **non-profit** users, staff with a PhD degree was the largest group within the laboratory unit, which is more than for profit, where staff with a PhD predominates in 20.9 % of laboratory units. Conversely, more **profit** users indicated that laboratory technicians make up the largest group within their unit (Figure 3). For both sectors only in few units the material is handled by personnel without training in microbiology, and in virtually none of the units people without training in biology predominate.

3.1.5. Quality Management Systems implemented by users (Q16)

In total, 739 respondents (67.0 %) declared to have a QMS in their laboratory unit (Figure 4) and most of them related to activities in microbiology.

The implementation of QMS differed greatly between sectors (Figure 5A). A higher proportion of **non-profit** users did not have a QMS (39.1 %). For those that had one, GLP (30.9 %) was most common, followed by a QMS not assessed by a third party (14.4 %) and ISO 9001 (12.1 %). In contrast, only 13.9 % of **profit** users did not have a QMS in place, and the standards applied mostly were ISO 9001 (39.7 %), GMP (24.0 %) and GLP (20.2 %). Figure 5B illustrates the proportion of the different systems that are related to activities in microbiology per sector. Other standards mentioned by respondents were ISO 13485 (9), ISO 15189 (3), ISO 22000 (2), and ISO 17043 (1).

3.1.6. Use of Genetic Resources (Q12)

Figure 6 shows the distribution of different types of GR used by respondents: mostly used in the past five years were **bacteria** (85.3 %), **yeasts** (42.3 %) and **filamentous fungi** (40.4 %). For these three GR types, respondents indicated a general decrease in use for the next five years, -17.8 % for bacteria and -5.9 % for both fungi and yeasts (Table 5). Also for other commonly used resources (>15 %), such as **genomic DNA** (-5.3 %), **plasmids** (-4.7 %), **animal cell lines** (-2.3 %) and **human cell lines** (-1.8 %), a decrease in use in the future was indicated by the respondents. The reason for this indicated decline was not asked and therefore currently unknown.

In contrast, for the less commonly used GR a slightly increased use was indicated for the future: **Archaea** (+2.4 %), **viruses** (animal, plant, and human) (+1.5 %), **Cyanobacteria** (+1.2 %), and **microalgae** (+0.5 %). Although these increases are small, a minor “shift” towards the less commonly used GR types can be expected in the future based on these numbers.

Other used GR mentioned by respondents were nematodes, plants, mites, and specific types of fungi or bacteria (e.g. mycorrhiza, anaerobes, phyto- and mycoplasma, Actinobacteria).

Table 5 Change in use of genetic resource users over time (difference between use in the past five years and the next five years)

Genetic resource	Difference between number of users at present and in the future	
	number of users	%
Bacteria	-209	-17.8
Filamentous fungi	-69	-5.9
Yeasts	-69	-5.9
Genomic DNA	-62	-5.3
Plasmids	-55	-4.7
Cell lines_animal	-27	-2.3
Cell lines_human	-21	-1.8
Hybridomas_animal	-6	-0.5
Protozoa	2	+0.2
Phages	3	+0.3
Viruses_human	4	+0.3
Lichens	5	+0.4
Cell lines_plants	5	+0.4
Hybridomas_human	5	+0.4
Micro-algae	6	+0.5
Viruses_animal	6	+0.5
Viruses_plants	7	+0.6
Cyanobacteria	14	+1.2
Archaea	28	+2.4

The past five years, especially yeasts and fungi were used relatively more by **profit** than by non-profit sector, in contrast with genomic DNA, plasmids, Archaea and phages, which were used relatively more by non-profit (Figure 7). Decreasing and increasing trends in use of the different GR over time was mostly similar for both sectors (not shown).

3.1.7. Applications of genetic resources (Q13)

The applications for which the GR were used considerably differed between the non-profit and profit **sector** (Figure 8): for the **non-profit sector**, the main applications were fundamental research (76.5 %), R&D (61.6 %) and teaching or training (48.6 %), whereas the **profit** group applied GR mostly for R&D (72.0 %), quality control (45.5 %) and commercial applications (43.6 %).

Figure 8. For which application(s) does your laboratory unit use microbial/genetic resources at present, and/or might use in the future? (Q13)

Answered: 1167
Multiple answers

3.1.8. Outsourcing of microbial analysis (Q17)

Figure 9A shows the relative differences between both profit and non-profit respondents that outsource particular microbial analyses **to any third party** (not necessarily to a CC). The analyses mostly outsourced are **DNA sequencing** (65.5 % non-profit and 43.0 % profit) and **identification** (40.7 % non-profit and 54.2 % profit). Other analyses outsourced by over 20 % of non-profit users were isolation of pure cultures, microbial count, whole genome/gene sequence analysis, real-time PCR and phenotypic characterization. Most analyses are outsourced relatively more by non-profit users, except for microbial count and isolation of pure cultures.

Other outsourced analyses that were mentioned by respondents included fluorescence microscopy, cloning, sequencing of large DNA fragments, MLVA/MLST, G+C content analysis, antibody production, and sensitivity testing (Annex 6, 6.6.2). These analyses may represent **potential gaps** in the analysis methods offered by service CCs.

Figure 9: Which microbial analyses does your Laboratory unit outsource at present, and/or intend to outsource in the future? (Q17)

Overall, the respondents checked more analyses they outsourced in the past five years (N = 4953), than they intend to outsource in the next five years (N = 4300). For most of the analyses listed, the figures generally show less outsourcing in the future for both sectors, with some exceptions. The **non-profit** group indicated to increase outsourcing of RNA sequencing (+2.4 %), whole genome sequence data analysis (+1.6 %), metabolite production (+1.5 %) and –omics related services (+0.5 %) (Table 6). In contrast to this trend in the non-profit sector, the profit sector indicated to decrease the outsourcing of whole genome sequence data analysis (-6.8 %) and RNA sequencing (-1.2 %) in the future. On the

other hand, profit users intend to increase outsourcing of enzyme production (+3.2 %), -omics studies (+2.4 %), fatty acid profiling (+2.0 %), DNA-DNA hybridization (+1.2), pathogenicity tests (+1.2 %), phylogenetic studies (+0.8 %), plasmid profile analysis of bacteria (+0.8 %) and metabolite production (+0.8 %).

Table 6: Change in outsourcing of microbial analyses over time (difference per sector between outsourcing in the past five years and the next five years)

Outsourced analyses	Difference in % of users at present and in the future	
	% Non-profit users (N = 792)	% Profit users (N = 249)
RNA sequencing	2.4	-1.2
Whole genome sequence data analysis	1.6	-6.8
Metabolite production	1.5	0.8
-omics	0.5	2.4
Real-time PCR	0.1	-0.8
Enzyme production	-2.7	3.2
Fatty acid profile (FAME-MIDI)	-2.9	2.0
DNA-DNA hybridization	-4.2	1.2
Pathogenicity tests	-1.1	1.2
Phylogenetic studies	-2.1	0.8
Plasmid profile analysis of bacteria	-0.4	0.8

3.2. Origin of the genetic resources used, and legal issues related to the CBD

3.2.1. Origin of the genetic resources used (Q18)

Respondents indicated that the **main source** of GR used was **the organization itself** (rating average of 2.3 = between “about half” and “most”) (Table7). This was the case for both the non-profit and the profit sector, although the **profit users rated service collections nearly as important as isolation by the organisation**. For most respondents, only some GR were obtained from research laboratories (average rating = 1.4). Private companies selling biological material were the least common source of GR for both profit and non-profit respondents.

Other relevant sources mentioned by 13 respondents were hospitals and clinical laboratories (Annex 6 (6.6.3)).

Table 7. Source of the GR used within laboratory units

Source of used GR	All users (N = 1034)	Non-profit (N = 791)	Profit (N = 243)
	RA ¹	RA	RA
From Service CCs	1.7	1.6	2.0
Isolated by your Organisation	2.3	2.4	2.1
From Research Laboratories	1.4	1.4	1.5
From Private Companies	1.3	1.2	1.4
Other (comment)	1.8	1.9	1.7

¹The Rating Average (RA) was calculated by multiplying the weighted value of each rating with the actual number of respondents who picked that rating, adding the totals and dividing it by the number of ratings given. The used weighted values were “Some” = 1, “About half” = 2, “Most” = 3, and “All” = 4.

3.2.2. Awareness of and compliance with the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (Q19-20, Q23)

Less than half (43 %) of respondents were **aware** of the CBD (from which 43.8 % of non-profit and 40.7 % of profit users).

31.2 % of non-profit and 23.4 % of profit users indicated to **always ask for PIC**, whereas respectively 21.4 % and 12.7 % **never** do (Figure 11).

Only a few respondents asking PIC “in some cases” gave a valid reason for this: they asked PIC only for strains isolated after the CBD. Other reasons given were mostly invalid, e.g. they asked PIC only for strains isolated abroad or from CBD signatory countries outside the EU, or only when strains are deposited in a CC, or only for pathogens and quarantine organisms (Annex 6, 6.6.4).

Most respondents indicating “never” or “not applicable” commented that they isolated resources only in their own country and not abroad (N = 50), or were unaware (N = 41). Other invalid reasons given for not asking PIC were: use of GR only internally, only isolated from the environment, or isolated only non-pathogens.

The invalid reasons clearly indicate limited knowledge of respondents on the obligations under the CBD.

Figure 11: In case your laboratory unit isolated microbial/genetic resources, did it ask Prior Informed Consent (PIC) from the appropriate authority in the country of origin of the sample according the CBD? (Q20)

Several respondents commented on the CBD (open question 23; see Annex 6, 6.6.6). The most relevant comments were:

- There is a lack of harmonisation between countries, since interpretation of the CBD is very country specific.
- The EU should find common rules and simplify existing procedures regulating access to GR. (in order to avoid more discarded material and publicise more valuable microorganisms, e.g. distribution of patented strains for research purposes, **not commercial purposes**).
- Contacting authorities in the country of origin can be problematic.
- Not only 3rd world countries should protect their resources.

3.2.3. Problems in obtaining microbial/genetic resources (Q21-22)

The problems in obtaining the required GR experienced most were “**difficulty to find a provider of the required resources**” and “**scientists reluctant to share their resources**”, although non-profit

respondents encountered the latter problem more often than profit respondents (50 % versus 32.9 %) (Figure 12). Although the least problems were experienced with principles of Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS), still 17.6 % of non-profit and 19.9 % of profit claimed to have experienced ABS related problems occasionally or frequently.

Figure 12: The most “frequently” and “occasionally” experienced problems in obtaining microbial/genetic resources (per sector) (Q21)

The main encountered problems relating to **difficulties to find a provider** were:

- For particular microorganisms there are **gaps** in the current offer (difficult to find), e.g. emerging or non-indigenous pathogens, certain strains of which the full genome has been sequenced, particular fungi of phylogenetic interest, rare material, multi-resistant clinical isolates, ...
- As a new comer in a research field, it is often difficult to obtain the required material if it is not commercially available, e.g. commonly used cell lines, GMOs, ...
- The use of different identifiers for the same material among providers impeding the search
- Lack of an international list of providers with current address
- For each required item a different provider has to be found
- Important or historical strains are sometimes lost because the research group/scientist is no longer active and/or the material has not been deposited

- Strain histories are difficult to ascertain from publications or provided information
- The provider of the required material has no distributor in the country of the user

The main encountered problems relating to **scientists reluctant to share their resources** were:

- Scientists refuse to share material because of various reasons:
 - they are apprehensive of losing the monopoly within their research field
 - they are linked to the commercial area
 - they have concerns about intellectual property rights
 - the recipient is a private company
 - publications get priority over the provision of diagnostic material to relevant sectors
- Some scientists ask unreasonable fees

The main encountered problems relating to **(missing) documentation of properties of resources** were:

- Information on growth requirements, biochemical/physiological/genetic/phenotypic properties, virulence capacity, plasmid maps, biosafety level, identification methods used, isolation source ... is sometimes poorly documented
- There is a lack of standardization in documentation of properties
- In many cases provided information is incorrect
- Information is not available in English
- Online search engines of collection catalogues can be difficult to use

The main encountered problems relating to **transport regulations** were:

- Regulations differ between countries and are often unclear or unavailable
- Difficulty to find transport companies for biological material in general, BSL3 organisms or dry ice
- Import permits are difficult to obtain and take a long time, e.g. for plant pathogens
- Problems with customs clearance

The main problems relating to **specific conditions in the MTA of the provider** were:

- The MTA is too complex, training is required
- The MTA is too restrictive
- The MTA requires full details on intended use
- The MTA is only available in a foreign language
- Lack of uniformity
- Bureaucratic issues to get the MTA approved by the recipient's own legal entity

The main problems relating to **biosecurity rules** were:

- Problems with quarantine, dual-use, newly described or unidentified microorganisms
- Lack of harmonized rules across countries
- Bureaucratic issues in own institute or that of the provider

- Difficulty to find the right contact within the authorizations/governmental office

The main problems relating to **principles of Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS)** were:

- Lack of a harmonized agreement in BS
- Delays in research because of negotiations or disputes
- Lack of contracts concerning strains isolated during projects
- Unrealistic estimates of potential benefits/royalties
- Limitations in determining microbial properties that could have commercial potential
- Limitations in use of primary clinical isolates
- Patent issues

Other relevant problems specified by users were:

- Problems with the quality of ordered material (misidentified or dead strains received from CCs, cell lines with mycoplasma contamination or with incorrect STR profile)

A complete overview of the responses to question 22, “Specify for each of the subjects in which you experienced problems in obtaining microbial/genetic resources, the nature of the problem”, is listed under Annex 6 (6.6.5).

3.3. Use of the services currently offered by CCs

3.3.1. Present and future use of services offered by CCs (Q24)

Overall, respondents checked more services they intended to order in the next five years (N = 2571) than services ordered in the past five years (N = 2386), indicating an increased interest of users in the services offered by CCs.

The top five of ordered services in **the past five years** were: (1) supply of biological material (59.3 %), (2) public deposit (45.0 %), (3) identification (19.0 %), (4) safe deposit (18.0 %), and (5) supply of genomic DNA (15.6%) (Figure 13).

Although respondents indicated a decreased demand for supply (-10.8 %) and public deposit (-3.3 %) of biological material in the future, for most services the demand was slightly **increased** in the future, with the largest increase for **deposit with patent purposes** (+6.0 %), **whole genome sequence analysis** (+3.7 %), **training** (+3.6 %), **safe deposit** (+2.8 %), **MALDI-TOF** (+2.7 %), and **-omics** (+2.5 %).

Figure 13. Regarding the services currently offered by CCs, please indicate which ones you ordered in the past, and which ones you intend to order in the future. (Q24)

Answered: 816

Table 8. Change in services ordered from CCs over time (difference per sector between services ordered in the past five years and the next five years)

Services ordered from CCs	Difference in % of users at present and in the future		
	% Non-profit users (N=634)	% Profit users (N=182)	% All users (N=816)
Deposit of biological material for patent purposes	+6.0	+6.0	+6.0
Whole genome sequence data analysis	+4.7	0.0	+3.7
Safe deposit of biological material	+3.2	+1.6	+2.8
-omics	+3.0	+0.5	+2.5
MALDI-TOF	+2.7	+2.7	+2.7
Training	+2.7	+6.6	+3.6
Gene sequence data analysis	+2.2	+1.1	+2.0
Metabolite production	+1.9	+2.7	+2.1
Pathogenicity tests	+1.9	+0.5	+1.6
RNA sequencing	+1.7	+2.2	+1.8
Phylogenetic studies	+1.4	-1.1	+0.9
DNA sequencing	+1.4	2.2	+1.6
Plasmid profile analysis of bacteria	+1.3	+1.1	+1.2
Enzyme production	+1.3	+2.7	+1.6
Ribotyping	+1.3	-1.6	+0.6
Real-time PCR	+1.3	0.0	+1.0
Phenotypic characterization	+0.9	+1.1	+1.0
RAPD	+0.9	-0.5	+0.6
Sequence analysis of non-characterized plasmids	+0.9	+0.5	+0.9
Screening for specific properties	+0.6	0.5	+0.6
Serotyping	+0.6	0.5	+0.6
Antibiotic sensitivity tests	+0.5	0.5	+0.5
Pulsed-field gel electrophoresis	+0.5	-0.5	+0.2
Consultancy	+0.2	+3.8	+1.0
Supply of genomic DNA	0.0	0.0	0.0
AFLP	0.0	-1.1	-0.2
Fatty acid profile (FAME-MIDI)	-0.3	+0.5	-0.1
Polar lipids	-0.5	0.0	-0.4
DNA-DNA hybridization	-0.6	-0.5	-0.6
Microbial count	-0.6	-2.7	-1.1
Identification	-0.9	+1.1	-0.5
Isolation of pure cultures	-1.3	-0.5	-1.1
Public deposit of biological material	-3.0	-4.4	-3.3
Supply of biological material	-10.7	-11.0	-10.8

Some services were ordered from CCs relatively more often by profit than non-profit users, especially identification, microbial count, deposit for patent purposes, consultancy and training (Figure 14). In contrast, the non-profit users made relatively more use of public deposit, DNA-DNA hybridisation, FAME-MIDI, polar lipid analysis, and supply of genomic DNA.

A complete list of the specified responses mentioned under “other” is given in Annex 6 (6.6.7).

Figure 14. Regarding the services currently offered by CCs, please indicate which ones you ordered from CCs in the past five years (per sector).

3.3.2. Problems, gaps and shortcomings in the services currently offered by CCs (Q25-27)

Most users (80.2-94.8%) declared not to order particular services offered by CCs because they were: “not needed” or “taken care of in house”. Most importantly, between 13.7 and 5.2 % of the users were “not aware” of the possibility of obtaining the proposed services from CCs.(Figure 15). “shortcomings” (e.g. price, time frame, administrative burden) or “gaps” (e.g. missing taxa, missing analyses) were given as a reason for not using a service in only 0.6-6 % and 0.3-0.9 % of cases, respectively (Figure 16).

The top five services **taken care of in house** were real-time PCR (45.9 %), identification (44.9 %), microbial counts (44.1 %), isolation of pure cultures (43.3 %) and phenotypic characterization (40.2 %). **Interestingly, identification was also indicated among the top three ordered services.**

The services of which respondents were least aware included DNA sequencing (13.7 %), training (13.1 %), supply of biological material (12.6 %), consultancy (11.9 %) and whole genome sequence data analysis (11.8 %). Table 9 focusses in detail on the services that are not known by at least 10 % of either profit or non-profit users. From table 9 follows that profit users are less aware of services offered by CCs. For example, almost 1/4th of the profit users indicated to be unaware that CCs offer training. Among non-profit users, DNA-sequencing services are not known by 13 % of the users, followed by supply of biological material (11.76 %).

Table 9. Services offered by CCs of which at least 10 % of either profit or non-profit users is not aware. (x = less than 10 %)

Not aware of service	% Profit	% Non-profit
Training	24.14	10.42
Consultancy	18.33	10.30
DNA sequencing	16.13	12.99
Supply of biological material	15.00	11.76
Identification	13.33	x
MALDI-TOF	11.59	x
Whole genome sequence data analysis	11.43	11.90
Metabolite production	11.43	x
Serotyping	10.77	x
Phenotypic characterization	10.61	x
Enzyme production	10.29	x
Pathogenicity tests	10.14	x
RAPD	10.00	x
Real-time PCR	10.00	x
RNA sequencing	x	x
-omics	x	10.12
Polar lipids	x	9.79

Figure 16 shows per service the number of respondents that indicated either “shortcomings” or “because of gaps”. Despite the considerable number of “shortcomings” indicated in the services ($N_{\text{all services}} = 205$), little clarifying answers were given by respondents when asked to describe them. “Price” was mostly mentioned as a shortcoming by 30 respondents (of which 28 were non-profit users) who specified that their funding was insufficient to outsource all required services or that the prices were considered too high (e.g. for training and consultancy, sequencing in general, fatty acid and polar lipids analysis, enzyme and metabolite production). “Time frame” and “administrative burden” both were specified by only eight and seven respondents respectively.

The description of “gaps” ($N_{\text{all services}} = 8$) based on the few open responses was even more difficult. Taxa or biological material missing in the catalogues was given as a reason by three respondents. One respondent specified that data related to the resources was missing (partial characterization of biological material).

Regarding “other shortcomings”, some respondents described that particular services are cheaper or faster in other and/or more local companies. One respondent mentioned in-site training as a shortcoming because he/she preferred online training. Other remarks were the lack of guidance to deal with problems when sending cultures due to custom regulations and that it was impossible to get payment documents in the own language (Russian).

Annex 6 (6.6.8 and 6.6.9) list the descriptions of the gaps and other shortcomings given by respondents.

Figure 15. In case your laboratory unit never ordered a particular service from culture collections in the past five years, please indicate the reason. (% of reasons given per service) (Q25)

Answered: 386

Figure 16. In case your laboratory unit never ordered a particular service from culture collections in the past five years, because of gaps or other shortcomings. (% of reasons given per service) (Q25)

3.3.3. Training services (Q28)

In general, 499 respondents confirmed their interest for one or more training services, the most valued ones being microbial identification and characterization, data analysis, and cultivation (Figure 17). For training in phenotyping respondents showed the least interest (12.6 %).

The specific topics required by profit and non-profit users were different. Profit users are highly interested in Microbial identification and characterization, Cultivation and Microbial detection and diagnostic techniques whereas non-profit users have a higher demand for Data analysis and Molecular tools.

Other useful training topics suggested by respondents were data analysis of whole genome sequencing, pyrosequencing, bioinformatics, and how to access data related to resources (Annex 6, 6.6.8)).

3.3.4. Information services (Q29-32)

Regarding the information that respondents expect to receive from CCs with respect to the biological material they offer, **scientific name** and **growth conditions** were rated “**indispensable**” by most respondents (Figure 18). Also, pathogenicity, accession number(s) in the other CC(s) and quarantine status in Europe are leaning towards an “indispensable” status, but are nevertheless chief among the topics that were considered “important”. This top five is closely followed by the nomenclatural status, substrate from which the biological material was isolated, physiological and biochemical properties, geographic origin, dual use status and morphology. Information regarding the depositor or isolator was ranked closest to “if available”.

Other relevant subjects commented by respondents were: related strains, synonyms, a summary of the description from literature (especially when journals have restricted access), method of isolation and number of subcultures (for fungi in particular), MALDI-TOF fingerprints, chemotaxonomic characteristics, secondary metabolites, preservation conditions, and risk group classification according to different countries’ legislation (Annex 6, 6.6.11).

Open access online was by far the most popular format to access information on the biological material offered by CCs (86.8 % of 833 respondents). Online access with a required user account was supported by 21.4 %, whereas hardcopy and CD-DVD only by respectively 8.3 % and 4.7 %. When asked which online tools users would like to see implemented, 65.7 % of 808 respondents were in favour of online data processing, and 60.8 % of data download for local processing. Other tools suggested by respondents included a search tool for all possible fields, a well described stable programmatic interface that is standardized across collections, and links to relevant databases (Annex 6, 6.6.12).

For 93.3 % of 719 respondents accession numbers linking to genes or genomes in public sequence repositories were relevant for their work, whereas links to protein and metabolic databases were relevant for respectively 56.3 % and 48.5 %. Other information linking the biological material’s phenotype to its genotype that was considered important included links to 16S/18S rRNA databases for taxonomic purposes, morphology and biochemical data, SNP databases, the global infectious diseases (Gideon) database, genetic profiles for cell identity, taxonomy and literature databases, and the gene expression omnibus (GEO) (Annex 6, 6.6.13).

¹Weighted values used: “Yes, if available” = 1; “Yes, important” = 2; “Yes, indispensable” = 3

3.3.5. Collaborative projects with CCs (Q33-35)

266 respondents indicated that their laboratory unit has collaborated with a service CC in research projects. Based on 215 responses from these 266 respondents (the other respondents skipped the question), the CC was a subcontractor in 58.1 % and a full partner in 45.1 % of these projects.

The projects were mainly financed by the own organization (54.3 %) or financed externally (46.1 %). 37.5% indicated that projects were co-financed by the partners' own budget (Figure 19).

3.3.6. Comments of users on services (Q36)

Several respondents took the opportunity to give additional feedback on services offered by CCs. Table 10 shows those comments.

Table 10. Comments about the services that CCs offer

“
There is a discrepancy between the requirement to deposit new species in two culture collections before publishing and the acceptance or possibilities to maintain fastidious bacteria (eg nitrite oxidizers).
Would be pleased to see improvements in the microbial banks as I am aware of the several cases where people purchased wrong bacteria from the bank. obviously, there are many erroneously assigned bacterial strains.
They need adequate funding, especially those requiring 'niche' services
We had also a problem with 2 bacterial strains that we sent for it public deposite and the Culture Collection lost these cultures so we had to send them twice.
It is important that they preserve strains properly that are used in research so that experiments can be repeated (i.e. vouchers). Or papers must give full details of where, and how strains were isolated and maintained so that other researchers can repeat these methods in attempts to find the same strains.
I am concerned at the absence of expert morpho-mycologists to check cultures are the correct organism even in many European centres. I am concerned at the current level of misidentifications, which feeds through into errors in GenBank on which many rely as an identification resource.

We use mainly the source of antibodies for immunologic assays, and viral, bacteria and fungal strains. The access to this service is essential to realize our work.
Our Laboratory unit is well equipped for microbial analyses, so the main services we require from a Culture Collection is the deposit of our own isolates and most possible information on microbial resources we want to acquire
Pathogenicity is very important feature for plant pathogens. Many isolates lost pathogenicity, so are not usable anymore
Public deposit must be very easier and feedback on identification must receive soon as possible with explanation and picture if possible
It takes too much time to receive the accession number.
Culture collections are very important components of modern science, and could become a highly valued partner in advancing science by making many studies more rapid and reproducible across many laboratories. All agencies supporting science have a responsibility to help in maintaining collections of cultures and genomic materials.
One of the reasons because there is a difficulty to reach to the technological information is the price some web-pages have to access the contents. In my opinion it could be free, or have to be registered, but without paying.
The services and extend of cultures by Culture Collections are mostly unknown.
Online searching the collection is very important from within the site and from Google results. Slight differences in name of an item/cells can often result in a failed search. Search flexibility is very important to make use of the full collection.
I suggest that leading culture collections like DSMZ should include developing countries research institutes in their project to contribute those countries to manage their own future project.
I have found the services excellent, but there's always room for improvement.
A single identifier (for species/strains) for all culture collections will massively enhance the ease of finding cultures and information about them and thus speed up research.
Keep prices reasonable. Speed up process times. Make more information on the microorganisms available. Don't restrict R&D with complex MTAs.
Mostly not needed for a large research university like ours

3.4. Commercial use of resources supplied by CCs

3.4.1. Benefit sharing with CCs (Q37-38)

Of 882 respondents, 99 (11.2 %) indicated that their laboratory unit has been using microbial/genetic resources supplied by a service CC for commercial purposes (Figure 20). Of this group, approximately 33.0 % said that the laboratory unit had an agreement with the CC on return of benefits resulting from the commercial use of the resources (Figure 21). About 1/3 of both profit and non-profit respondents

has an agreement with the CC on return of benefits resulting from the commercial use of microbial/genetic resource(s) supplied by the CC (Figure 21).

3.4.2. Convention on biological Diversity (Q39-41)

When asked about their awareness of the recommendations for fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of microbial/genetic resources according to the CBD, 61.5 % of 876 respondents said not to be aware (Figure 22). Of 310 respondents that were aware, 26.5 % (82) said that these recommendations applied to the resources used by their laboratory unit for commercial purposes, 38.4 % (119) did not know, and 35.2 % (109) said the recommendations did not apply (Figure 23).

Several remarks were made by respondents on commercial use of resources supplied by CCs (overview of those open responses).

- *“I think it is sometimes over the top - collections should be a source of information for research and not a way of making money for the institution which it seems to become more and more. Researchers deposited their strains to share them with the scientific community but this thought seems to be superseded by the urge to create profit by institutions and individuals therein. A certain cost of the service is acceptable as culture collections involve a lot of work - but certain "rights" some collections think they have are not in line with the original mission of such collections and the researchers who deposit their strains with them.”*
- *“The origin of microbes is often impossible to trace exactly. For example one can extract microbes from open markets that sell all kinds of food, coming from all over the world. It is then expected that the*

corresponding microbes come from the place where they have been bought, not their possible place of origin (often quite impossible to identify rigorously)”

- *“Don't restrict commercial R&D with unrealistic and complex profit sharing expectations and regulations.”*
- *“CBD and ABS is the sovereign right of the provider country and CBD/ABS issues therefore needs to be in agreement with that country, not the culture collection.”*
- *“Commercial entities should purchase any resources (and use licenses) that they use directly from the Collection, rather than from non-commercial scientists.”*
- *“As culture collections get the fee for deposit of strains, no other further fee for commercial use is needed.”*
- *“It is very important that this service exists and is improved.”*
- *“More exchangeable information between different Culture Collections”*
- *“Service culture collection centres should be supply details like which are the most effective strain for specific insect or plant pathogen etc.”*
- *“Our Laboratory unit is mainly involved in fundamental research, and has so far made no commercial use of microbial resources from Culture Collections”*
- *“We do not cultivate and/ or resell cells/bacteria. Our commercial benefit is made by selling photos we make from the organisms. So this seems to be "out of" the benefit-sharing meant by CBD.”*
- *“We use the biological resources as controls of our trials.”*
- *“We only use them for research purposes.”*

4. MAIN CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Data presented in this document is the basis for further inter-WP related actions. From this point of view, it should be **emphasized that other WP-members should go through the report** and use all relevant information for their respective tasks and deliverables.

Regarding the MIRRI offer

- **Potential gaps in GR and related services were assessed.** Respondents indicated that some particular resources and analyses are difficult to find, which may represent gaps in the offer or difficulties to find the provider. A **MIRRI portal** with integrated catalogues and a common service charter would foster visibility and help users in localizing the correct provider. Moreover, it would help MIRRI providers in identifying the real gaps.
- **Resources cited in publications** are often not available in service CCs. Users claim difficulties to access these kind of resources, because scientists are reluctant to share them or because the group has already disappeared. In this regard, MIRRI shall pursue two strategies; to work closer with scientist and facilitate the deposit of “key” strains (those cited in publications or with special properties) and to convince policy makers and journal editors about the necessity of obligating authors to deposit published resources and important resources isolated with public funds.
- Some users indicated the difficulty to find providers of **fastidious organisms** and some **specialized services** currently not offered by MIRRI partners. MIRRI should work closely with research laboratories in order to help them achieve the desired level of quality to become partners of the RI or learn from their experience and broaden their offer.
- Harmonization and extension of the **data sets** associated to the genetic resources was also indicated as an important issue for the users. They also suggest to use unique identifiers for equivalent strains in different collections. MIRRI shall work on the **integration of the catalogues** from the different providers and try to connect resources with as much information as possible, including links to other databases.
- A **MIRRI access policy** for increasing capacity avoiding redundancy would help broadening the offer in a rational way, increasing efficiency while optimizing resources.

Regarding legal aspects related with the use of microbial genetic resources

- Users would welcome a **common, simple and not too restrictive MTA**. In addition, users indicated problems with IPR/ABS/confidentiality issues of the providers’ or holders’ MTA and with the administrative process of getting the MTA signed by their organization (difficulty to identify the responsible, administrative burden, etc.). Clear and harmonized information would solve some of these problems.
- More than half of the respondents were not aware of the Convention on Biological Diversity (**CBD**) (57 %) and of the principles for Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from the Utilization of GR (**ABS**) (61%). In addition, some respondents that declared to know about these international agreements gave invalid responses to the question “did you asked for PIC?”

(Q20), confirming the lack of information about these topics. Considering the fact that many (between about half and most) of the resources are isolated by the users' organizations, this indicates that they may have not been acting diligently with regard to the Nagoya Protocol. To help solving this problem, MIRRI should develop a mandatory **Policy for the partners in compliance with the CBD**, which would guarantee due diligence for the users utilizing MIRRI resources. Moreover, an expert platform dealing with these issues would help delivering the right messages and increase the awareness of users. .

- Users indicate problems and disinformation about **transportation** of the genetic resources (custom clearance, difficulty to find carriers) and **biosecurity** issues (mainly quarantine and dual-use organisms). They are especially displeased due to the different regulations and lack of transparency in several countries. MIRRI shall provide clear and user-friendly information about the applicable regulations in different countries and shall lobby for transparent rules about the cross-border transport of the resources.

5. REFERENCES

OECD (2001) *“Biological Resource Centres: underpinning the future of life sciences and biotechnology”*.

6. ANNEXES

6.1. Annex 1: MIRRI-WP2 User questionnaire

MIRRI Statement on use, access and protection of collected data

1. Do you accept the MIRRI Statement on use, access and protection of collected data? *[Y; N]*
2. Do you want to answer this questionnaire anonymously? *[Y; N]*

General Information

3. Give the full name of your Organization.
4. Give the name of the Department or Section in which your laboratory is included within the Organization, if applicable.
5. Give the full name and complete address of your Laboratory unit. *[Full name; Address; City/Town; State/Province; ZIP/Postal Code; Country]*
6. Give your name, function, email address and phone number. *[Name; Function; Email Address; Phone Number]*
7. If different from the person filling in this questionnaire, give the name, function and contact information of the appropriate person to discuss your Laboratory unit's future needs regarding microbial resources and related services. *[Name; Function; Email Address; Phone Number]*

User profile

8. To which sector does your Organization belong? *[Profit sector; Non-profit sector]*
9. In case your Organization belongs to the profit sector, what is the size of your enterprise? *[Micro-enterprise (less than 10 employees); Small to Medium size enterprise (between 10 and 250 employees); Large enterprise (more than 250 employees)]*
10. In case your Organization belongs to the non-profit sector, to which organization type does your Organization belong? *[University; School; Hospital; Control or Reference Analyses laboratory (e.g. health, diagnostic, inspection, official controls); Research Institute; Foundation; Other (comment)]*
11. To which field of activity does your Laboratory unit belong? *[Research & Education; Agronomy; Bioremediation; Chemical; Environmental; Food & Feed; Pharma & Medical; Veterinary; Other (comment)]*
12. Which kind of microbial/genetic resource(s) does your Laboratory unit use at present (the past five years), and/or might use in the future (the next five years)? *[Archaea; Bacteria; Cell lines_animal; Cell lines_human; Cell lines_plants; Cyanobacteria; Filamentous fungi; Genomic*

ANNEX 1: Questionnaire

DNA; Hybridomas_animal; Hybridomas_human; Lichens; Micro-algae; Phages; Plasmids; Protozoa; Viruses_animal; Viruses_human; Viruses_plants; Yeasts; Other (comment)]

- Used in the past five years
- Intend to use in the next five years

13. For which application(s) does your Laboratory unit use microbial/genetic resources at present (the past five years), and/or might use in future (the next five years)? *[Fundamental research; Research & Development; Commercial applications; Diagnostics; Quality control; Teaching or Training; Other (comment)]*

- Used in the past five years
- Intend to use in the next five years

14. What are the qualification levels in microbiology of the laboratory staff handling the microbial/genetic material in your Laboratory unit? *[No training in microbiology; Laboratory technician; University degree; PhD degree; Other (comment)]*

15. Which one of the mentioned qualification levels dominates in your Laboratory unit? *[No training in microbiology; Laboratory technician; University degree; PhD degree; Other]*

16. Which Quality Management System (QMS) is in place at your Laboratory unit? Is it related to activities in microbiology? *[No QMS in the laboratory; QMS not assessed by Third Party (no certification or accreditation) ; ISO 9001; ISO 17025; ISO 14000; ISO Guide 34; Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP); Good Laboratory Practice (GLP); Other (comment)]*

- In place
- Related to activities in microbiology

17. Which microbial analyses does your Laboratory unit outsource (to any third party, not necessarily to service Culture Collections) at present (the past five years), and/or intend to outsource in the future (the next five years)? *[Isolation of pure cultures; Microbial count; Identification; Phylogenetic studies; Phenotypic characterization; DNA sequencing; Whole genome sequence data analysis; Gene sequence data analysis ; RNA sequencing; Plasmid profile analysis of bacteria; Sequence analysis of non-characterized plasmids; DNA-DNA hybridization; Pulsed-field gel electrophoresis; RAPD; AFLP; Ribotyping; Real-time PCR; Serotyping; Fatty acid profile (FAME-MIDI); MALDI-TOF; Polar lipids; Metabolite production; Enzyme production; Pathogenicity tests; Antibiotic sensitivity tests; -omics; Screening for specific properties; Consultancy; Training; Other (comment)]*

- Outsourced in the past five years
- Intend to outsource in the next five years

Origin of the microbial/genetic resources used / Legal issue related to the CBD

ANNEX 1: Questionnaire

18. Where are the microbial/genetic resources that are used within your Laboratory unit sourced from? *[Isolated by your Organisation; From Research Laboratories; From Service Culture Collections; From Private Companies; Other (comment)]*

- None
- Some
- About half
- Most
- All

19. Are you aware of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)? *[Y;N]*

20. In case your Laboratory unit isolated microbial/genetic resources, did it ask Prior Informed Consent (PIC) from the appropriate authority in the country of origin of the sample, according to the CBD? *[Always; In some cases (comment); Never (comment); Not Applicable (comment)]*

21. Did your Laboratory unit experience any problems in obtaining microbial/genetic resources? *[Specific conditions in the Material Transfer Agreement of the provider; Principles of Access and Benefit Sharing; Biosecurity rules; Transport regulations; Scientists reluctant to share their resources; Difficulty to find the provider of the required resources; Lack of documented properties of the resources; Other problems]*

- Never
- Occasionally
- Frequently

22. Specify for each of the subjects in which you experienced problems in obtaining microbial/genetic resources, the nature of the problem. *[Specific conditions in the Material Transfer Agreement of the provider; Principles of Access and Benefit Sharing; Biosecurity rules; Transport regulations; Scientists reluctant to share their resources; Difficulty to find the provider of the required resources; Lack of documented properties of the resources; Other problems]*

23. Do you have additional comments to share about the origin of microbial/genetic resources that your Laboratory unit uses and/or legal issues related to the CBD? *[comment]*

Use of the services that Culture Collections currently offer

24. Regarding the services currently offered by Culture Collections, please indicate which ones you ordered from Culture Collections in the past five years, and which ones you intend to order from Culture Collections in the next five years. *[Public deposit of biological material; Safe deposit of biological material; Deposit of biological material for patent purposes; Supply of biological material; Supply of genomic DNA; Isolation of pure cultures; Microbial count; Identification; Phylogenetic studies; Phenotypic characterization; DNA sequencing; Whole genome sequence data analysis; Gene sequence data analysis; RNA sequencing; Plasmid profile]*

ANNEX 1: Questionnaire

analysis of bacteria; Sequence analysis of non-characterized plasmids; DNA-DNA hybridization; Pulsed-field gel electrophoresis; RAPD; AFLP; Ribotyping; Real-time PCR, Serotyping; Fatty acid profile (FAME-MIDI); MALDI-TOF; Polar lipids; Metabolite production; Enzyme production; Pathogenicity tests; Antibiotic sensitivity tests; -omics; Screening for specific properties; Consultancy; Training; Other (comment)]

- Ordered in the past five years
- Intend to order in the next five years

25. In case your Laboratory unit never ordered a particular service from Culture Collections in the past five years, please indicate the reason. *[Public deposit of biological material; Safe deposit of biological material; Deposit of biological material for patent purposes; Supply of biological material; Supply of genomic DNA; Isolation of pure cultures; Microbial count; Identification; Phylogenetic studies; Phenotypic characterization; DNA sequencing; Whole genome sequence data analysis; Gene sequence data analysis; RNA sequencing; Plasmid profile analysis of bacteria; Sequence analysis of non-characterized plasmids; DNA-DNA hybridization; Pulsed-field gel electrophoresis; RAPD; AFLP; Ribotyping; Real-time PCR; Serotyping; Fatty acid profile (FAME-MIDI); MALDI-TOF; Polar lipids; Metabolite production; Enzyme production; Pathogenicity tests; Antibiotic sensitivity tests; -omics; Screening for specific properties; Consultancy; Training]*

- Not aware of
- Because of gaps (e.g. missing taxa, missing analyses)
- Because of other shortcomings (e.g. price, time frame, administrative burden)
- Is taken care of inhouse
- Not needed

26. In case you have indicated 'because of gaps' for any of the services in the previous question, describe these gaps in a few words in the corresponding textbox(es). *[Biological material not accepted for deposit; Taxa or biological material missing in catalogues; Missing analyses; Missing data related to the resources ; Other]*

27. In case you have indicated 'because of other shortcomings' for any of the services, describe these shortcomings in a few words in the corresponding textbox(es). *[Price; Time frame; Administrative burden; Other]*

28. In case you would use the training service in the next five years, what kind of training program(s) would be useful for your Laboratory unit? *[Data analysis; Taxonomy; Cultivation (e.g. anaerobic, fermenters, intracellular bacteria); Preservation; Molecular tools; Genotyping; Phenotyping; Culture collection management; Microbial identification and characterization; Handling of hazardous microorganisms; Risk assessment; Microbial detection and diagnostic techniques; Legal aspects related to the microbial/genetic resources; Other (comment)]*

29. On which subjects do you expect to receive information from the Culture Collections, with respect to the biological material they offer? *[Scientific name; Authors of the scientific name; Year of publication of the scientific name; Nomenclatural status of the strain (e.g. holotype,*

ANNEX 1: Questionnaire

neotype, pathovar); Isolator; Depositor; Date of deposit in the Culture Collection; History (from isolation to arrival at the Culture Collection); Accession number(s) in other Culture Collection(s); Geographic origin; Substrate from which the biological resource was isolated; Date of sampling; Date of isolation; Growth conditions; Pathogenicity; Quarantine status in Europe; Dual-use status in Europe; Patent references; Gene sequences; Full genome sequence; Literature References; Morphology; Photos, images, pictures; Physiological and biochemical properties; Applications; Other (comment)]

- Not required
- Yes, if available
- Yes, important
- Yes, indispensable

30. In which format(s) do you prefer to access the information on the biological material offered by the Culture Collections? [*Hardcopy; CD-DVD; Online (open access); Online (user account required)*]

31. In case the Culture Collection presents information on its biological material online, which tools would you like to see implemented? [*Data download to process data locally; Online data processing; Other (comment)*]

32. What kind of information, linking the phenotype of the biological material to its genotype, is of relevance for your work? [*Accession numbers linking to genes or genomes in public sequence repositories (e.g. EMBL, GenBank); Links to protein databases (e.g. UniProt); Links to metabolic databases (e.g. KEGG); Other (comment)*]

33. Has your Laboratory unit already collaborated with a service Culture Collection in research projects? [*Y; N*]

34. What was/were the source(s) of financing of the research project(s)? [*Financed only by your Organization; Co-financed by the project partners' own budgets; Financed externally (e.g. by European Commission)*]

35. Was the service Culture Collection in these research projects a full partner or a subcontractor? [*Full partner; Subcontractor*]

36. Do you have additional comments to share about the services that Culture Collections offer? [*comment*]

Commercial use of the microbial/genetic resources supplied by service Culture Collections

37. Is your Laboratory unit using for commercial purposes microbial/genetic resource(s) that were supplied by a service Culture Collection? [*Y; N*]

38. Does your Laboratory unit have an agreement with the service Culture Collection on return of benefits resulting from the commercial use of these microbial/genetic resources? [*Y; N*]

ANNEX 1: Questionnaire

39. Are you aware of the recommendations for fair and equitable Sharing of Benefits arising from the utilization of microbial/genetic resources, according to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)? [*Y; N*]

40. Do these recommendations for fair and equitable Sharing of Benefits apply to the microbial/genetic resources used by your Laboratory unit for commercial purposes? [*Y; N*]

41. Do you have additional comments to share about the commercial use of microbial/genetic resources supplied by service Culture Collections? [*comment*]

6.2. Annex 2: Statement on use, access and protection of collected data

Online survey to define the function and content of the Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure, MIRRI

1. What information will be collected, for what purpose and by what means?

The MIRRI survey gathers information from European microbial/genetic Resource Centres and their Users, aiming to define the function and the content of MIRRI and to provide means for efficient and co-ordinated access to the microbial/genetic resources, their derivatives, and associated data and services.

The survey results will also be used to improve quality standards, harmonization in data storage and collection management.

The survey consists of a number of questions, uploaded by means of an application in a set format (SurveyMonkey). After the collection period the survey is closed and no further answers are possible. The raw data are subsequently transferred to a local database in form of an Excel table for further analyses, or are analyzed manually. All analyses are depersonalized to ensure that no connection with the participant can be made at the level of the name of the individual and at the level of the name of the company/institution.

For this survey the following data will be collected:

- a) Information from microbial/genetic Resource Centres about their structure, staff, holdings, services offered, Quality Management System, legal issues related to their activity, future perspectives, etc.
- b) Information from Users of microbial/genetic Resource Centres (researchers, public institutions and private companies) about their sector of activity, size, staff qualification, and – most importantly - their present experience and their future needs and expectations in relation with the services provided by microbial/genetic Resource Centres.

The Questionnaires related to the survey are not anonymous by default. Although all analyses will be depersonalized, it is also possible to complete the User-questionnaire anonymously, by marking the corresponding box at the start of the questions.

In that case, please observe that MIRRI cannot contact you anymore for further dialogue on your needs and expectations.

2. Who has access to your information and to whom is it disclosed?

ANNEX 2: MIRRI Statement

The raw data gathered in this survey are accessible only to a strictly limited number of members of the MIRRI preparatory phase consortium, responsible for the data analyses.

The identity of the persons filling in the questionnaire and of their Company/Institution will not be made public, and will only be divulged within the MIRRI consortium and only to those MIRRI partners on a need to know basis for further direct communication/contact in the frame of the MIRRI project.

The information freely communicated within and outside the MIRRI project shall be visible as read only documents and shall be digested and anonymised both at the level of the personal names as at the level of the company/institution name.

The digested and anonymised information will be delivered to the European Commission, as an output (Deliverable) from the MIRRI preparatory phase project.

3. How do we protect and safeguard your information?

Access to the Questionnaire contents is limited to the members of MIRRI Work package 2 responsible for the upload of the questions and download of the responses, and is controlled via 'active directory authentication' (username and password). Access to the Personal Computer with the local database with raw data is limited to the system administrator and the local MIRRI research associates, and is controlled by username and password. Backups are made on an external device used only for this purpose, and will be deleted as described in (4).

4. How long do we keep your data?

Individual responses (raw data) will be deleted from databases at the latest 1 year after after the digested output (Deliverable) has been reported to and accepted by the European Commission.

5. How can you access, verify, modify or delete your data?

To verify, modify, correct or delete any personal data you can contact VeerleS.Piessens@ugent.be, by sending an e-mail giving details of your request.

ANNEX 3: MIRRI Culture Collections

6.3. Annex 3: List of Culture Collections participating in the MIRRI preparatory phase project

Culture Collection Acronym	Full name	Country	MIRRI status
ACA-DC	Agricultural University of Athens - Agricultural College of Athens - Dairy Collection	Greece	collaborating party
ATHUM	Culture Collection of Fungi	Greece	collaborating party
BCCM-IHEM	Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms - Biomedical fungi and yeasts collection	Belgium	collaborating party
BCCM-LMBP	Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms - Plasmid and DNA Library collection	Belgium	collaborating party
BCCM-LMG	Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms - Bacteria Collection	Belgium	full partner
BCCM-MUCL	Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms - Agro-industrial fungi and yeasts collection	Belgium	collaborating party
CABI	Centre for Agricultural Bioscience International	UK	full partner
CBS	CBS-KNAW Fungal Biodiversity Centre (Centraalbureau voor Schimmelcultures)	The Netherlands	full partner
CCF	Culture Collection of Fungi	Czech Republic	collaborating party
CCIM-IAFB	Culture Collection Of Industrial Microorganisms	Poland	full partner
CCUG	Culture Collection University of Gothenburg	Sweden	full partner
CCY	Culture Collection of Yeasts	Slovakia	collaborating party
CECT	Spanish Type Culture Collection	Spain	full partner
CIP-CRBIP	Biological Resources Center of Pasteur Institute	France	full partner
CIRM-BIA	Centre International de Ressources Microbiennes - Bactéries d'Intérêts Alimentaires	France	full partner
CIRM-BP	International Centre of Microbial Ressources - Pathogenic Bacteria	France	full partner
CIRM-CF	Centre International de Ressources Microbiennes Champignons Filamenteux	France	full partner
CIRM-CFBP	French Collection for Plant-associated Bacteria	France	full partner
CIRM-Levures	Centre International de Ressources Microbiennes - Levures	France	full partner
DBVPG	DBVPG Industrial Yeasts Collection	Italy	collaborating party
DSMZ	Leibniz-Institut DSMZ Deutsche Sammlung für Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen GmbH	Germany	full partner
ICLC	Interlab Cell Line Collection	Italy	full partner
IEGM	Regional Specialized Collection of Alkanotrophic Microorganisms	Russian Federation	collaborating party
ITEM	Agri-Food Toxigenic Fungi Culture Collection	Italy	collaborating party

ANNEX 3: MIRRI Culture Collections

Culture Collection Acronym	Full name	Country	MIRRI status
MSCL	Microbial Strain Collection of Latvia	Latvia	collaborating party
MUM	Micoteca da Universidade do Minho	Portugal	full partner
MUT	Mycotheca Universitatis Taurinensis	Italy	full partner
NCAIM	National Collection of Agricultural and Industrial Microorganisms	Hungary	collaborating party
NCIMB	National Collection of Industrial Food and Marine Bacteria	UK	collaborating party
PCM	Polish Collection of Microorganisms	Poland	collaborating party
PYCC	Portuguese Yeast Culture Collection	Portugal	collaborating party
SAG	Culture Collection of Algae at Göttingen University	Germany	collaborating party
VKM	All-Russian Collection of Microorganisms	Russian Federation	full partner
VTCC	Technical Research Centre of Finland Culture Collection	Finland	collaborating party

6.4. Annex 4: List of National Scientific Associations

Country	Acronym	National Association	Website
AUSTRIA	ÖGHMP	Austrian Society of Hygiene, Microbiology and Preventive Medicine	www.oeghmp.at
BELGIUM	BSM	Belgian Society for Microbiology	www.belsocmicrobio.be
	BSFM	Belgian Society for Food Microbiology	www.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/bsfm
	BVMDM	Belgische Vereniging voor Menselijke en Dierlijke Mycologie	www.medmycol.be
	FABI	Fédération Royale des Associations Belges d'Ingénieurs civils, d'ingénieurs agronomes et bio-ingénieurs	www.fabi.be
	FF	Flandersfood	www.flandersfood.com
	FlandersBio	FlandersBio	www.flandersbio.be
	Food2know	Food2know	www.food2know.be
	SBIMC/BVIKM	Belgium Society of Infectious Diseases and Clinical Microbiology	www.sbimc.org
BULGARIA	BAS	Bulgarian Society for Microbiology (Union of Scientists in Bulgaria)	www.microbio.bas.bg
CROATIA	HMD	Croatian Microbiological Society	www.hmd-cms.hr
CZECH REPUBLIC	CSSM	Czechoslovak Society for Microbiology	www.cssm.info
DENMARK		Danish Microbiological Society	www.dmselskab.dk/
ESTONIA	EBS	Estonian Society for Microbiology	www.ut.ee/et
FINLAND	BIOBIO	Finnish Society of Biochemistry	www.biobio.org
FRANCE	SFM	French Society of Microbiology	www.sfm.asso.fr
	SMF	French Society of Mycology	-
	SFP	French Society of Parasitology	www.sfparasitologie.u-psud.fr
GERMANY	DGMH	German Society of Hygiene and Microbiology	www.dghm.org
	GfV	Society of Virology (Austria, Germany & Switzerland)	www.g-f-v.org/
	VAAM	Association for General and Applied Microbiology	www.vaam.de
GREECE	HMS	Hellenic Microbiological Society	www.hms.org.gr
HUNGARY	MMT	Hungarian Society of Microbiology	www.mmt.org.hu

ANNEX 4: List of National Scientific Associations

Country	Acronym	National Association	Website
ICELAND		The Microbiological Society of Iceland	www.orfi.is
ISRAEL		Israel National Committee for Microbiology	-
		Israeli Society for Microbiology	www.ism.org.il
ITALY	AMCLI	Italian Association of Clinical Microbiology	www.amcli.it
	SIMGBM	Italian Society of General Microbiology and Microbial Biotechnology	-
	SIM	Italian Society of Microbiology	www.societasim.org
	Assobiotech	Italian Association for the Development of Biotechnology	assobiotec.federchimica.it
IRELAND	ISCM	Irish Society of Clinical Microbiologists	www.iscm.ie
LATVIA		Latvian Society for Microbiology	-
LITHUANIA	LMS	Lithuanian Microbiological Society	www.lms.lt/lms
MACEDONIA		Macedonian Microbiological Society	-
THE NETHERLANDS	NVVM	Royal Netherlands Society for Microbiology	www.nvvm-online.nl
	NVMM	Netherlands Society for Medical Microbiology	www.nvmm.nl
	KNPV	Royal Netherlands Phytopathological Society	www.knpv.org
	NBV	Netherlands Biotechnological Society	nbv.kncv.nl
	NVBMB	Netherlands Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology	nvbmb.kncv.nl
NORWAY	NFM	Norwegian Society for Microbiology	www.nfmikro.net
POLAND	PTM	Polish Society of Microbiologists	www.microbiology.pl
PORTUGAL	SPM	Portuguese Society for Microbiology.	www.spmicrobiologia.pt
	OB	Professional body for biologists	www.ordembilogos.pt
	SPB	Portuguese Society for Biochemistry	www.spb.pt
	SPDIM	Portuguese Society for Infectious Disease and Clinical Microbiology	spdimc.org
	SPBT	Portuguese Society for Biotechnology	www.spbt.pt
	OE	Professional body for engineers	www.ordemengenheiros.pt
	SPV	Portuguese Society for Virology	www.spv.pt
	APBIO	Portuguese Association for Bioindustries	www.apbio.pt

ANNEX 4: List of National Scientific Associations

Country	Acronym	National Association	Website
	ASPOMM	Portuguese Association for Medical Micology	ecmm.eu/ASPOMM
	AMAP	Mycology Association "A Pantorra"	www.pantorra.pt
	OM	Professional body for medical doctors	www.ordemosmedicos.pt
	ACL	Academy of Science of Lisboa	www.acad-ciencias.pt
	APBG	Portuguese Association of Biology and Geology Professors	www.appbg.pt
	OMV	Professional body for veterinary surgeon	www.omv.pt
	SPCV	Portuguese Society for Veterinary Science	www.spcvet.pt
ROMANIA	SRM	Romanian Society for Microbiology	www.srm.ro
RUSSIA	RSB	Russian Society of Biotechnologists	biorosinfo.com
	IRMS	Interregional Russian Microbiological Society	old.inmi.ru/Microbsociety/societyeng.htm
	VNPOEMP	Scientific and Public Health Society of epidemiologists, microbiologists and parasitologists of Russia	www.vnpoemp.ru
	RNAM	All-Russian National Academy of Mycology	www.mycology.ru
SLOVENIA		Slovenian Microbiological Society	www.smd.si
SPAIN	SEM	Spanish Society for Microbiology	www.semicrobiologia.org
	SEF	Sociedad Española de Fitopatología	www.sef.es
	SEBBM	Sociedad Española de Bioquímica y Biología Molecular	www.sebbm.es
SWEDEN	SFM	Swedish Society for Microbiology	www.mikrobiologi.net
SWITZERLAND	SGM-SSM	Swiss Society for Microbiology	www.swissmicrobiology.ch
TURKEY	TMC	Turkish Microbiological Society	www.tmc-online.org
UNITED KINGDOM	BMS	British Mycological Society	www.britmycolsoc.org.uk

6.5. Annex 5: List of International Scientific Associations

Acronym	International Association	Website
ISME	International Society for Microbial Ecology	www.isme-microbes.org
IOBB	International Organisation for Biotechnology & Bioengineering	www.iobbnet.org
EuropaBio	European association of bioindustries	www.europabio.org
EFB	European Federation of Biotechnology	http://www.efb-central.org/
FEMS	Federation of European Microbiological Societies	www.fems-microbiology.org
IUMS	International Union of Microbiological Societies	www.iums.org
ESCMID	European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases	www.escmid.org
IBBS	International Biodeterioration and Biodegradation Society	www.ibbsonline.org

6.6. Annex 6: Overview “comments or other responses per question” (if applicable)

6.6.1. Q11 “To which field of activity does your Laboratory unit belong ?”

Aerospatial
biodeterioration of archives and libraries
Biotechnology
Biotechnology
Biotechnology
Biotechnology
Biotechnology, Biodiscovery
BIOTECHNOLOGY, NANOTECHNOLOGY
Consumer Goods
cosmetic
cosmetics
Cosmetics
development
diagnostic
Diagnostics
Doping control analysis
Fast moving consumer goods
flavours and perfumes industry
IVD industry
Kosmetik und Haushaltsreiniger
manufacturing
Oil and Gas
production of fungal spores for biocontrol product
Quality Control
Quality Lab for different microbiological tests
R&D related to Mining and Minerals technology
Technical support
testing materials against microbial attack
textile finishing
wine

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

6.6.2. Q17 “Which microbial analyses does your laboratory unit outsource (to any third party, not necessarily to service Culture Collections) at present (the past five years), and/or intend to outsource in the future (the next five years)?

DNA DNA Hybridization
DNA sequencing of clones; DNA sequencing of large fragments ("chromosome walking")
service only on noncommercial base, only for scientific purposes
Storage
Antimicrobial products sensitivity tests and also sensitivity tests in relation to heavy metals
Fluorescence microscopy analysis
ELISA et IC PCR
Obtaining and depositing identified filamentous fungi.
Cloning
Providing of pure cultures
MLVA, MLST
GC %
Deposit to obtained a number of strain for publication
storage of specific strains, use of type strains
metals resistance
Purification of genomic DNA for bacteria and archea
G+C content analysis
Cytotoxicity assays with K562 cells
Respiratory quinones DNA base composition
Heat resistance determinations
Gene/plasmid synthesis
G+C content, Analysis of quinones, mycolic acid, polar lipids, peptidoglycan structure, cell Wall sugars
Microbial standard tests according to ASTM, SN, BS, JIS and CEN/DIN
antibody production

6.6.3. Q18 Where are the microbial/genetic resources that are used within your Laboratory unit sourced from?

Environmental isolates from the factory
authors of new taxa description
From researchers
I only know about CABI
CCF Prague, Czech republic
Hospital laboratory
central hospitals from the region
MR4
used for routine analyses for positive controls from state organisations
generated by recombinant DNA technology (plasmids, S. cerevisiae)
Oxoid, Chemie Brunschwig, MesaLabs(USA)
most micro-organism are genetically modified in house.
Patient specimens
Collaborators

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

nature throughout the world
enviromental
Other University Hospitals from France or other countries
Patient samples
hospitals
Diagnostic human and veterinary laboratories
External Health Service Organizations
Clinical Microbiology Hospital Laboratories.
Kombucha is a public domain product
clinical laboratories
Other Hospitals: strain collections to be typed for epidemiological purposes
Hospital laboratories
Clinical samples from hospitals

6.6.4. Q20 In case your Laboratory unit isolated microbial/genetic resources, did it ask Prior Informed Consent (PIC) from the appropriate authority in the country of origin of the sample, according to the CBD?

No microbial/genetic resources have been isolated by my Organisation
Samples provided by our clients. Whether they asked PIC is doubtful.
I don't see why I should ask prior informed consent ?? and I nevertheless don't agree with this idea
When isolated by ourselves, only from locally produced crops.
The original sample is from same company
complicated, takes a long time
for type strains, we are allowed to deposit
We comply with South Africa's laws under the Biodiversity Act of 2004.
isolation from enrichment that had been handed down twice from the lab collecting the sample; that 3rd party lab did not obtain PIC (for bureaucratic difficulties)
We do not isolate resources out side India
we do not isolate new strains
ONLY WHEN I THINK THAT MICROORGANISMS WILL BE DANGEROUS FOR HUMAN HEALTH
The institution no our laboratory asks always the PIC, no the laboratory
Where appropriate
Microbial resources are isolated from food, water or environmental samples.
isolates stem from native invertebrates
Some strains are older than CBD
Quarantine bacteria
It just applicable in protected areas
non pathogenic
They are all clinical isolates obtained for diagnostic purposes
When isolates are obtained from individuals involved in clinical studies, feeding or diversity studies, the consent forms cover us to use/keep isolates obtained (part of the requirements of the human tissue act (UK-specific)). We get verbal consent to use/keep isolates recovered from members of the laboratory (most of our work deals with faecal bacteria).
In cases where biological resources were isolated in countries outside the EU, the studies were always done in collaboration with colleagues from the country from which the resources were isolated.
We have been working under EU projects rules
not regulated in our country
Chile doesn't ask for informed constant to work with enviromental samples.
It is aked when the isolated microbial is gping to be deposited in a Culture collection

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Salmonella serotyping
we isolate strains from fermented products produced by our lab
Was informed we didn't need one for material collected in the USA
pure yeast cultures used. No isolation intends
we have not isolated mos from nature
ask PIC when we isolate microbial resources from abroad.
During dedicated studies
We do not isolate micro-organisms from nature.
The only isolates we obtaine from outside Austrakia are sourced from culture collections and comne via quarantine. All these would have the required constent agreements with them
This is a public research institution of Sicily: it is not for profit and has the aim of increasing the production of wine and olive oil in Sicily. The microorganisms are isolated from local sources and are used mainly for research purposes. Those few that are marketed produce profits that are used according to the Italian laws. The profits in favor of the Institute are invested back into research
not necessary in our case
Depends on whetherin own country or from others that require this.
Obtained from other primary isolators
Isolates have not been made publically available
countries that require this
No commercial benefits
only domestic samples used.
In some cases owners of land where plant material was sampled for the isolation of fungi were notified.
Organisms isolated for further study are typically isolated from own country. Isolation of microbes from samples from other countries is typically for enumeration purposes only (as part of a collaborative project), not for further study or exploitation.
We do not isolate microbial/genetic resources from nature
has not been done yet
Our Laboratory unit have been authorized from the appropriate authority ("Consejería de Agricultura y Pesca") to realize this work
I microoganismi isolati dal nostro ente sono ambientali e mantenuti per periodi determinati.
Trading company that work mainly with customer's samples or own bacteria certified strains
Consulting with the staff of our yeast collection.
complicated
Always filled out the requested forms asked for, not sure if it was according to PIC or CBD
If none colleague from the country of sample origin is involved in the publication.
We produce and isolate recombinant E. coli and influenza viruses in house
We are working on fungi.
we work sample directly for us costumer in the enological fild
Isolated from artisanal dairy products
We are not isolated genetic and the microbial have only internal use
laboratorio oficial de diagnóstico.
all strains are isolated from medical or environmental material upon the necessary consent of the providers as means to complete analysis that is contracted.
Isolated as part of routine diagnostic service for competent authority within State
Microbial resources isolated from substrates available in the internal area of the company
Sampling campaigns have been done in the context of a EU research project. Permits and benefits have been agreed following the rules of the EU guidelines.
organisms were isolated from commercially available sources
Resources are being isolated in the course of partnership-based research project.
Microbes isolated from soil samples not specific to the country of origin of the sample.
environmental strainght
resources isoalted from samples from private companies
Kombucha is a public domain product
Quarantine or risk assessed materials
In have never asked for permission according to CBD.

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Our Laboratory realize microbiological determinations in food to verify observance of legislation. We work with well-known microorganisms
We do quality control inspections for pathogens
For the genetic plant resources we can trace every seedlot, from commercial seed or from genebanks. For diseases wo do not ask a PIC to the authority in the country of origin of the sample. It's not clear to me by who I have to ask permission when diseases can be isolated from commercial traded vegetables. We are aware of quarantaine diseases, we deal with them very strictly and according to the quarantaine rules.
the strains stayed in the laboratory
We use standard bacteria to monitor food contamination.
only isolation within own country, sometimes within neighbour EU country
We normally work with species very common in nature related with plants
Our bacterial and fungal isolates come only from agricultural fields
permission is necessary to sample collection for the projects which is supported by government
State Phytosanitary administration
we don't isolate bacteria from specimen coming from outside of our industry.
isolated from local products or environment
Isolation was carried out within an official public-funded research project.
Medial Ethical Committee approval is needed prior to patient sampling
We only isolated it though 3rd parties taking care of the CBD aspects
I have no insight into every case that occurred within our laboratory.
Cultivated organisms from Yellowstone National Park are covered by a Material Transfer Agreement with the US National Park Service.
Cultures available from own culture collection
We sterilize our waste
used for internal purpose only
Personally, I have no overview.
Were not aware of it. Coutry of origin of the sample was same country where isolation took place and organism was submitted to a culture collection.
all older than CBD
not necessary for my research
Only for scientific study
Most isolates are from Portugal, we ask permits for those that are isolated abroad
We only isolate from materials that originate within our own country.
Isolated by mutagenesis, selection or screening of pure microbial strains.
Isolations are performed mainly for the indentification of pathogens during food quality/safety analysis
Our work does not affect the Biological Diversity
sampling allowance
Our isolates are from food/feed materials either freely traded in the EU or deliberately sent to us.
When clinical studies are performed
1- mostly handling within-borders national samples (dealing with foreign samples is exceptional) 2- ownership of samples and isolated strains is (shortly) defined in the 'terms of analysis' agreed between the lab and its clients 3- not aware of nay (belgian) competent national authorities (CNAs) granting prior informed consent
we do not work with hazardous substances
When resources are taken from Government owned land
The source of the genetic material does not fall under this remit.
outside Portugal
From CBD signatory countries outside the core EU
I received resources by exchange between CCs and by general deposit.
I'm unaware if we isolated any novel genetic material from any other country
there is no regulation in the university.
not necessary for cell lines and recombinant viruses for gene transfer and shRNA knockdown
In the case of EU funded projects, the CBD guidelines were considered. In addition we did
depends on researcher/depositor

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

6.6.5. Q22 Specify for each of the subjects in which you experienced problems in obtaining microbial/genetic resources, the nature of the problem.

1. Specific conditions in the Material Transfer Agreement of the provider

administrative slowness
Agreement too restrictive
all rights stay with provider
Bureaucratic process in having MTA approved from our offices
Calibration reference material not appropriate for arrays that are intended to control
Certain organizations draft MTAs that are too restrictive
Clause preventing making of a glycerol stock for own usage
Clauses imposed by the depositor
Clauses, especially relating to publication, continuing supply of results to donor (when not a collaboration) or modification of resources supplied, or applicable legal systems - all conditions we or our institution may object to
Complicate to transfer material to other collaborator after getting cultures
complicated administrative rules, higher requirements for training
Complicated procedures and name of the rector of the university needed (too high in hierarchy to deal with these things)
conditions regarding publication of work using the resource
Conditions to be used even for non profit use very strict
Contributing author on research
custom problems
Deal with professionals in this sector
different MTAs in different labs/research institutes
Difficult to understand english law talk
Difficulties for signature of the MTA
don't recall details
DSMZ biosafe level 2 strains,MTA are protect by Europe.It's can't supply to CHINA. But the other collection can did it.
Due to material transfer agreement the material is restricted
E.g. ATCC material transfer agreements have varied over the years and one has to be very cautious to look at the right version.
Fargoing claines on rights on results from own research, not compatibel with University and grant agencies
Foreign law
Genetic resources from wild Alliums from Greece
ie ATCC has a MTA that restricts commercial research
In principal we don't use recources which only can be obtained under a MTA
in some cases it was asked that we give a detailed account of what we were doing, while this is incompatible with confidentiality
Industrial property
IP issues
It takes a long time going through legal procedures
Legal agreement
legal discussion
legal jargon between the organizations was not agreed upon
Legal language and non-publishing clauses
Legal requirements and IP rights
lengthy paperwork
limitations in the utilization
Limitations of use of the strains purchased
limited
limited use

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Limiting experiments to be done
limits in use, sometimes very restrictive
material may be required to be destroyed; no transfer possible
MTA agreements have not been a problem for research use of the material
MTA had to be altered
MTA is very strict in what resource may be use for, limiting research outputs
MTA not available
MTAs in foreign language only,
Need to ask for permission before publishing
No legal representative was assigned to sign the document / person-in-charge had no experience in this matter
no uniformity of procedures
Not agreed upon by my institution.
Not Kown the appropriate authority
Not possible to buy from US supplier
Often pointless paperwork slowed by lawyers
Organization disagree on conditions but usually a compromise could be reached
our administration often insist of negotiating conditions
over-reaching expectations for IP control
Ownership and what can be done with the mo and what not
patents
Personal cooperation
PHYTOSANITARY RISK
Place of deposit of name-bearing types where there is no adequate centre in the country
Problems with IP office
Providers sometimes don't have MTA's organised to accomplish the rules
Provision of legal accreditation
Publication delay
research agreements
Restricted commercialization
restricted use, publications
rights of industrial and intellectual properties
scientific investigations developing in a direction, not yet considered at the moment of signing the MTA of the provider
Shipping across borders
some bacreria and fungies are not save viability on plates following transportation by post.
Some countries such as Argentina and Brazil have strick rules regarding the ransfer of the material.
Some times too strict
Sometimes profit organisations are not allowed to use the organism
Sometimes, difficult to obtain all documents they ask us for
Terms of agreement for commercial use
The ATCC has very severe restrictions on their strains, so I avoid the ATCC
The conditions may be too restrictive
the database gives MTA was only available for public organization
The MTA being unacceptable to out technology transfer office
The provider didn't disclosure the conditions.
Time consuming, Paperwork
To restrictive/expensive
Too much burocracy
Too restrictive
Too restrictive, stifled collaborative research

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

too restrictive, too much IP wanted from the usage
TRANSPORT CONDITIONS
try to incorporate ridiculous ownership claims and any subsequent research
unacceptable demand of publications numbers
Very complex MTA requirements, limiting public availability
Very difficult to get MTA for Universities secondary to publication
Very tedious when material has been originated in USA and Canada
We needed an ATCC level 3 biosafety material, and the provider don't help us about the customs in spite if they charged us too much money

2. Principles of Access and Benefit Sharing

Would not send published strains unless paid \$500 a strain.
very expensive
unreasonable expectations restrict access
Unrealistic expectations on size of benefit sharing (royalties).
Took very long to close a license agreement with a university.
The patent Microbe can't supply.....So sordidly!
the ownership terms between the lab and its client can be conflictual/contradictory
sometimes hard to get approval from CFIA for import
sometimes access is on the basis of strain exchange that have to be discussed. Some countries do not permit strains going out the country
Sometimes
Some research projects have not had a contract on how to deal with strains isolated in the projects.
Some people do not want to share
Some Culture Collection have lost the strain that we sent for deposit
share many
Researchers unwilling to give plasmids/cell lines even after publication - often citing patenting issues with funder
research agreements
processes too slow
People unaware of CBD
only when you have to specified the new characteristics of a product.
often negotiations can be lengthy, resulting in delayed research
Not interested in working with commercial companies
no universal agreement
multiple institutions
long exchanges with lawyers to find an agreement
Limit to the freedom for assessing properties with potential commercial interest
Lack on knowledge from provider and lack of value understanding by authorities
Lack of references
Lack of people able to give correct/clear information and to clarify doubts
It takes a long time going through legal procedures
IP
Indian strains unavailable
In some case, the contract for Sharing is indistinct.
Import from Brazil and Asia (strains)
I don't know what this statement means
exchange of material only
Disputes over the potential benefits concerning research using a particular microbe.

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

difficult to establish an agreement between parts
Difficult to obtain free use of primary clinical isolates
Complicated agreements in FP7
Complicate to transfer material to other collaborator after getting cultures, transfer permit complicated
co-authorship requests
Claims of rights
Certain researchers simply do not wish to share strains even if they published on them
Benefit Sharing with academics often exaggerated
all rights stay with provider
a company wants all the results and wanted to decide if we can publish or not

3. Biosecurity rules

Additional administration and loss of time.
Australian quarantine restrictions
Biosafety level, and bioterrorism problems
BSL2 clearance
Canary Islands needs air transport of samples and it is expensive.
Can't work with certain Clostridium spp. because of UK bioterrorism rules
carezza di informazioni
Complicated
complicated administrative rules, higher requirements for training
Crossing the Russian border with any biological resources demands at least 5 different official papers from various ministries for every spicement; therefore, the legal transportation is practically impossible; same is true for posting - practically omissible
custom
Deliveries have been blocked by local customs regulations
depending on the country and Institue: respect of French / EU rules
different biosecurity rules in different countries
different rules for different countries
differs from MRC to MRC. BSL ? German Trba ? which one to trust ? Where to find legal requirements
difficulties in ascertaining the risk groups of novel bacterial species isolated from healthy individuals
difficulty to get the autorization for import from the belgian authority
difficuly finding correct rules
Due to working with pathogenic multiresistant bacteria
excessive burocracy of our own institute
Exchange is sometimes difficult because different regulations in different countries
Foetal bovine serum required as part of US collaboration not available for sale in Europe
for tranfer of quarantine organisms on plants
from Switzerland to European countries
Government rules to import bacterial islates
Have not worked with highly pathogenic organisms
HIGH COST OF LAB EQUIPMENT
high risk groups
host lab does not always have necessary safety level
I think there isnt the information enough
Import from New Zealand
Import restrictions from non EU sources
Importation of possible plant pathogens under USDA/APHIS permits
importation regulations and approval process with CFIA

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Imported plant virus isolates may not be replicated in vivo or in vitro
In the case of pathogens
Inability to get Australian Quarantine Permit for specific plant pathogens
information for courier has to be provided
Inhouse constrictions to work with BSLlevel 3 microorganisms
internal regulations
International rules are difficult to deal with
Isolated resource found to be pathogenic after 16S identification or cannot be classed otherwise due to similarities.
It has been difficult to report plant pathogenic strains to the authorities due to their lack of knowledge on the matter.
it is understandable that due to biosecurity rules, the laboratory is not certified to work with/obtain specific microbial resources.
It takes a long time going through legal procedures
lack of information about changes of the risk group of a specific MO (TRBA 466 or 460)
Lack of regulation in same countries
lack of respect of regulations by persons
Legal Processes takes more time
Mainly related to transport.
Materials can not be exported or imported
Mostly exporting and importing outside EU to USA, NZ
Not always clear! , Q-organism: solutions for diagnostic controls are needed (i.e truncated micro, partially cloned etc)
obey
Official texts confused or too much strict
Our facilities are limited to BSL2
Our facility has optimal biosafety facilities
Over-regulation in relation to perceived Plant Health risks of unidentified and unassessed organisms
Pathogens risk
Pertaining to import permits in USA, China, Japan, India, Korea
PHYTOSANITARY RISK
plantpathogenic bacteria on the list of bioterrorism organisms
Premises obtains from governmental officers: difficulties to find the right contact
problem with level 2 et level 3 living pathogen. Not all center offer genomic DNA
Problems to get of some strains in some countries and need to acquire in other country
problems with German and US customs for import of cell lines with fetal calf serum
Problems with obtaining import permit
Problems with some pathogenic bacteria
prohibition of transfer of certain quarantine strains for the EU border
Protocols are not always clear nor easily available
Provision of papers according to regulations
purchase of microbial toxins abroad
quarantine
quarantine
quarantine pathogens from US (dual-use pathogens)
Quarantine regulations
quarantine regulations in Australia
Regulatory agencies in Saudi Arabia are not very familiar with this type of material
Required to send permits etc.
Restrictions regarding CDC category A agents
Rules to tight
S2 regulations sometimes cumbersome
safety issues GMO

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Shipment of even non-pathogenic bacteria to US
Shipment to USA especially difficult.
Some cultures of plant parasites are restricted for shipment.
Some isolates from ATCC are not available to UK companies
Some mo are not well typed in other countries and can cause a problem once arrived in the lab
Some pathogens are not allowed to be sent outside some countries. E.coli able to survive in fruit juices not found in Europe was not possible to get it from USA.
Some rules in China we can't import hazardous biological material.
Sometimes we had problems related to risk 3 microorganisms. We have a biosafety lab level 3 and we need to certificate our facilities. Sometimes different nations have different biosecurity rules or code strains differently (e.g., level 1 strain in one country might be a level 2 strain in another)
special permits are sometimes required.
specific countries are not allowed to send out material
STEC strains for first line control could not be sent abroad
strains in specific categories cannot be shipped
tedious documentation
The government is very strict for importing particular microbial/genetic resources
The provider sometimes does not know the biosafety level of the strain (we can only handle up to BSL2)
The rules keep changing - nothing consistent
These make getting import permits difficult to obtain, particularly for unclassified isolates to work with plant pathogens that are listed as not present in the country, in spite that they are here. Import of these microorganisms, or diverse plant material susceptible of harboring them, is problematic
too expensive and too exigent with low flexibility and some times unnecessary to be so strict
Too strict security rules
Transfer into the US from EU culture collections must pass customs. Forms from CDC sometimes needed.
transport at 4C in and out of the US was difficult
transport of pathogens
US scientists not willing to handle paperwork to ship strains
vary from country to country
Very tedious and involvement unnecessary time and paperwork
We are aware that Australian biosecurity limits what can be brought into Australia
we can not get magnaporthe strains from us because they are on bioterrorist agent list
we can not send or receive microbial resources whose biosecurity levels higher than 2.
We follow them
We have too low biosecurity for some strains and some projects we would like to do
we work on L1 bacteria, so that there is no problem of biosecurity
Were denied permission to transport organisms by government body

4. Transport regulations

between Switzerland and Germany for Staphylococcus aureus
biosafety issues GMO
blockage at the custom
Can be very expensive compared to the price of the strains
carencia di informazioni
Collaborators unaware of regulations
Coming to US they confiscated all the isolates
Complicated and difficult to know the rules
conditions of transport
costums often interfere with transport of viable/useable biomatter

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Country specific regulations
Courier refusing to transport material due to
Couriers and customs hostile to living organisms even if harmless
courriers that do not agree to transport
custom
Custom office
customs
customs
Customs
customs and local laws hinder the import of this material
Customs clearance
Customs clearance delaying transit. Couriers unwilling to handle dry ice packages.
Customs problems for mailing living organisms, and taxes for imports.
customs regulation
Delay of delivery to US laboratory of non-pathogenic strains
Deliveries have been blocked by local customs regulations
Deliveries stopped at customs
depending on regulations of the country, some strains are difficult to transport
depending on the country and Institute respect of French / EU rules
Desconocimiento o no aceptación por la otra parte
Different rules to import/export infectious substances for different countries
difficulty to identify appropriate transport
Difficulté si besoin carboglace
Difficulties are mainly by plane
Difficulties in shipping microorganisms even though non-pathogenic
Difficulties in shipping organisms with unknown risk groups
difficulties in transport of BSL3 microbes
Difficulties with custom authorities
difficulty finding correct rules and documents
Difficulty of obtaining courier services
Do not have required APHIS PPQ permit
Documentation to custom
due to the absence of a proforma invoice
European import regulations re serum-containing material atrocious!!!
Expensive
For some of the strains there were some problems to be sent
Freeze strains can't transport to China.
from Switzerland to European countries
frozen material with CO2
German customs confiscate materials
german customs stopped delivery, but with the right documents the delivery was continued
Have had some problems acquiring certain federal permits for certain strains.
Have not worked with highly pathogenic organisms
IATA
import into CH from non EU countries
import regulations, halt at customs
importation regulations with CFIA
Importing delays
Impossible to work with plant pathogens and follow USDA regulations

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

In the case of pathogens
Inceased price and documentation needed for type II strains
insufficient declaration by the sender
Inter- and intra-state shipping permits required.
Inter-country transportation
International samples get held up in customs. Are the storage conditions right?
It takes a long time going through legal procedures
It takes long time for insepection in imported country
lack of communication between US Customs and USDA
Lack of instructions/labels for transport
lack of knowledge of applicable legislation from staff at boder controls
lack of respect of regulations by personels
Lack of specificity. Difficult, not straightforward.
Lack of understanding between the two parties, which transport rules would apply
Lack of unified cross-border transport regulations
long costoms procedures
long time in custom for those who came from EEUU
mainly with countries like China and Brazil
microorganisms held at custom
Miscommunication between transport companies
Misplaced concern by port-of entry officals
misunderstandings by customs officers
Mostly paperwork issues with authorities, or papers lost during transport
mostly very difficult to transport pathogenic cultures
National and International regulations
obey
obtaining the right forms
Official texts do not foresee specific situations
One time Customs asked for specific documents to justify the entrance of the cultures
Paper work required to obtain bacterial strain not on file with FedEx tor eceive strains from Canadian group. Faxed paperwork and promptly received strains.
Parcels open with all documents but without the biological materials
permits
Pertaining to import permits in USA, China, Japan, India, Korea
PHYTOSANITARY RISK
postal office regulations
Problems due to shiping cultures from a company from another country
problems with customs forms and handling by third (courier) party
problems with German and US customs for import of cell lines with fetal calf serum
Problems with obtaining import permit
Problems with transport to other country with other rules for transportation resources.
products in dry ice
quarantine
Receiving/sending samples from/to some countries may be difficult (ex. India)
regulations a mess in Spain
Regulations change for different countries, protocols not easily available nor clear enough
Regulatory agencies in Saudi Arabia are not very familiar with this type of material
related to biosecurity rules
Required import permits take excesively long to obtain
Security rules for air transport

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Shipments retained at customers offices
Shipping and customs issues
Some cultures must be transported by courier and not mail
some of customs regulatiuon
some pathogen can't be shipped to an other contry
some problems in customs regulations
Some problems with document of biosecurity
some times biologic samples cause for concern
some times we experience customs delays to to some times vague customs regulations
Sometimes it is difficult to find a transport company which transport biological materials
Sometimes there are dificulties in delivery of the type bacterial strains by express-mail because custom officers consider them as goods.
Special packaging
special permits are sometimes required.
specific packages and rules
Specific transport for BSL3 very expensive!
Specific transporter needed.
standards unclear
stop by customs for some country
strain blocked under way
Strikes, bad wheather, delays
Taxes and customs arrangements
tedious documentation, adouanes
the package was held by the customs for a long time
The transport regulations should be universal, well-defined and widely disseminated to the Post and Custom authorities.
This relates to different nations having different biosecurity rules or code strains differently (e.g., level 1 strain in one country might be a level 2 strain in another)
time to get cultures
too burocratic and confused, too complicated
too many restrictions
Too strict regulation of transport of microorganisms
Transport of pathogens
Transportation on different Country
Transports from the US to Europe are sometimes difficult to conduct.
vary from country to country some especially difficult i.e. Canada and Australia
very complicated and handled differently in all countries or even states/Länder (Germany)
Very tedious and involvement unnecessary time and paperwork
we can not sent glass materials or activate microbial resources via the express delivery.
Were denied permission to transport organisms by government body
what is necessary to sent a MO, a GVO, a MO Riskgroup 2 in europe and over the world, declarations for sending over sea

5. Scientists reluctant to share their resources

a strain which is mentioned in a publication is often/sometimes not send if you ask for it
Afraid of competition
Agreed but never sent the sources
argue absence of samples
AS a rule of thumb from Japan (some Taphrinas)
as private company, some public organization does provide resources to private company

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

bad will
Certain researchers simply do not wish to share strains even if they published on them
common problem
competition
confidentiality
Constant delays in providing material isolated in other labs
Difficulty negotiating licensing fees
difficulty separating from his collection
difficulty to get (or to buy) rare, unique strains from local collection
Don't answer to petitions
Don't want to share
E-mails requesting cultures are ignored and go unanswered.
Emails to paper authors about "public" resources are not returned.
E-mails were never answered.
especially for hepatitis E virus from some Japanese labs
even though published, did not respond to requests
First publications instead of providing diagnostics for the relevant sectors..!
for unpublished papers, culture collections can not distribute without authors permission. though already in papers in press section
frequently
happens occasionally
Have asked for cultures from a number of Universities and not received
I have been confronted to it a few times, I could only speculate on the causes, this would not be of much use.
If it is published it should be made available
If there is any possible profit in the findings, chances are big that the resources are unavailable, unless a common project is set up
In my experience most scientists do not like to share their microbiological resources
in several cases the owners refused to give or sell their material because we are private
Individual scientists that are not aware about MTA's and international regulations
IP
it can happen ...
It happened once
It has happened twice in the last 6 years
It is really impossible in many cases to obtain resources for other scientists; sometimes they agreed but at the end they do not send the resource
Japanese scientists have overvalued for their resources. Some are expensive. We can't pay for their resources.
Lack of knowledge on the matter
Lack of response to emails asking for DNA/cultures
Lack of willingness to share strains/plasmids
Little communication among private laboratories, difficult access to University
long communication time, eventually dropped
many scientists cannot be bothered to even answer a request to share cultures, plasmids, etc
many scientists give their tools to companies, i.e. it is impossible to obtain tools for generation of recombinant Sendai virus because these rights have been transferred to a company (LIFE TECHNOLOGIES) who is selling these recombinant viruses of IPS cell generation
maybe conflict of interest
Mutants and strains described in papers not available to the community.
Never answered or possibly only able to supply the material later (what never happened).
no access to published products
No always received answer from scientist
no answer
NO answer from some scientists
no answer to inquiries

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

no answer to petitions
no answer when requested
No answer, delays...
No contestan
no fare reasons
no idea; reluctant scientist was just as reluctant to specify the nature of his reluctance
No or negative answers to the requests
no or very slow response
no reaction
no reply
no reply to request is frequent, or material said as not existing anymore
No response when you ask for a specific strain mentioned in scientific publications
no response from scientists
no response from scientists
no response or no willing to share
No response to email inquiries regarding obtaining published strains and or plasmids
no response to Email requests
No response to requests for strains
not all scientist willing share their strains
Not answering e-mails requesting strains
Not everyone wants to share the resources
occasionally they refuse to send materials
occasional refusal to send strains or 'forgetting" to do so
Often the idea that resources will be appropriated rules over interest in joint work
Once a research group was unwilling to share their resource due to copyright reasons
One instance in which we were denied sharing of a published resource because the scientist wanted to work in the same area that we proposed and did not want to collaborate.
one strain not deposited in a culture collection, was difficult to obtain a pure culture from the original isolator
Only occasionally. Students need to complete work.
Only once, from Japan.
Or do not answer inquiries related to strains
Overestimation of the value of the material
Pending on patenting/publishg the strain
people are afraid of sharing their strains and they don't send them to public collections
people are not willing to share
People don't answer their email
Perceived conflict of interests
Pertaining to claims in publications where strains were not available on request, as they were not viable or not kept.
Possibly competition preventing sharing.
probably afraid of competition
protected knowledge
Publications sometimes don ot mention, where to obtain the discribed material.
Publishing author refused to provide a published strain despite demand from Senior Editor of publishing journal
rarely
refused to give their samples or simply did not answer the request
Refusing to send material (GMO's) on request
Requests are not answered.
Required agreement on confidentiality and sharing of outcomes
Researchers unwilling to give plasmids/cell lines even after publication or requiring obstructive MTA - often due to funders
resources are necessary to his research

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

resources have been published, but later on used for commercial purposes
samples under study
scientific or some database do not provide the strain to private company
Scientist agree to share the material but never send it
Scientists are reluctant to share their sources because they are usually not included as coauthors of the publications.
scientists are very often linked to commercial area and are not willing to transfer cultures
Scientists do not answer your request
Scientists don't want to share strains of their culture collection
Scientists either ignore my requests to share strains, or charge unreasonable fee.
Scientists in certain countries typically do not deposit isolates in a publically accessible culture collection
Scientists unwilling to make available subcultures because of intellectual property concerns or to preclude others working on the same strains
scientists working on the same subject of research (competition)
self explaining
self explanatory
Sometimes scientists ignore requests for shared material
share strains of isolated bacteria
Simply no response to requests
Some colleagues do not answer the request
Some did not want to share published material
some full genome strains are not available to the community
Some of the strains asked for never arrived o directly yu recieve no answer
some people in some country discriminate the eminent lab.
some problems
some researchers did not want to provide us with the organism, because they were working on it themselves
Some scientist do not sen the published plasmids
Some scientists are just difficult
Some scientists are just mean, or too busy and they forget to answer your mails, or to send you the materials
Some scientists are very reticent to share their resources.
some scientists do no respond to inquiries about cultures
Some scientists do not like to share being afraid of losing monopoly of their research
Some scientists do not like to share isolates mainly those that have been mentioned in publications but not properly described
some scientists do not respond to requests
Some scientists do not respond when are requested for providing some materials
some scientists simply ignored my requests
Some scientists want to keep the strains they have isolated to themselves.
Some times too much barriers
Some will not supply strains requested no matter what you do.
sometimes happens
Sometimes it is not possible to received strains described in publications
sometimes no reply
sometimes no response
sometimes no response to request for strains
Sometimes the strain(s) requested to Colleagues are not available due to different reasons
Sometimes they do not want to share their resources
Sometimes.
strain was not a property fo the Institution to which resercher belonged
strains published but never sent (relates to only one occasion)
strains used in publications can not be obtained
the "customer's" sampling source for the isolates can be withheld to preserve shared IPR/publication

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

The authors either do not provide all the data or methods include erroneous data in the procedures
The patent Microbe can't supply.....So sordidly!
The strains were not available, or false
they are generally want to exchange the resources
They just do not answer emails..
They never replied or it was so complicated the procedure we found a different source
This is not always unreasonable, mostly scientists may need reassurance as to your intentions
Unwilling to send/share published bacterial strains
usually relating to mouse lines
Usually, no replies.
Very common problem with academics
Very common with academics who perceive companies as predatory
we have only accesses available strains
When the organisms are not in a collection is difficult to get them
When you read scientific publications it's hard to repeat the trial: I wonder if I do start with the same genetic resources.
willing to share only on written contract

6. Difficulty to find the provider of the required resources

"first owner" or initial discoverer not identified
a mutant gene for selection marker was circulated amongst scientists as a gift and being an amateur in the field it was little difficult to obtain it
Absence de réponse des dépositaires des souches
At right prices
ATCC equivalent
ATCC not great with anaerobes.
ATCC providers in Europe
authors would not respond to requests (email, fax, letter/post)
Bacterial strains are sometimes hard to obtain in living culture
bad documentation, unknown collection
Certified reference material
chines or african sources
cn't find genomic dna for some parasites or strain which require specific growth conditions
Common cell lines not available commercially. Must track down a lab that will send it.
difficulty to trace the author possessing the material
Difficult to cultivate MO like Helicobacter
difficulties in tracking current address of scientists describing microbial strains
difficulties to identify the original provider and obtain informations about the resources
Difficulty to find bacterial strains used as controls
difficulty to find quantified (oo)kysts of Giardia and Cryptosporidium (for QC)
Difficulty to find reference species in culture collections for certain taxonomic groups
DNA of pathogens
Don't exist in the catalog
E.coli able to survive in fruit juices not found in Europe
email doesn't work
especially those strains isolated more than one hundred years ago
Established collections incomplete for non-indigenous pathogens
for plasmids and phage, mainly
For some bacteria of veterinary origin

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

for some viruses
Foreign culture collections
frequently
Genomic DNA for desired bacterial species not available through service culture collections.
Google and Pubmed sometimes do not help
Google most often helps
Had to search hard and ask numerous people/companies
Hard to track down some species.
I had this problem before I found your company
if labs do not exist anymore or if culture collections do not have the specific strain
if so it will be dropped
In instances where labs have closed or people have moved on and their collections have been destroyed
incomplete references in publications
Increasing economic cost or not sending to the islands (prices)
Information gathered from scientific paper is sometimes outdated, and it can be difficult to get in touch with the researcher stocking a culture used in the publication
Isolates not present in culture collections; cost too high for an academic laboratory.
it concerns mostly resources used by Chinese scientists
It happened we were unable to find any collection with a strain that was mentioned in a scientific paper as being deposited in a collection.
it occurred particularly when people were retiring
it would be necessary a common data base where to find microorganisms
Japanese scientists is secrecy. There is little information of their project.
Lack of complete information
Lack of information for some providers (no internet catalogue)
Lack of information in the publication regarding the provider of the strain
language or source reporting makes collaboration or contact difficult
long online search
Looking for a specific cell line
many collections have disappeared (some institutions require that the investigators empty their laboratories when they leave!)
Many fungi of interest in phylogenetic studies are not yet available in any microbial culture collection
many strains have several names, most usually no more accessible
Microbial resource not easy to find
Ministry of Cultural heritage in Italy is poor
Mostly locating the person/institute where the line can be obtained
need to establish protocols with the hospital to collect the microorganisms they isolate from patients
new species of organisms
No address available or no response
No central port, for each micro-organism contact yet another research group!
No common database
no every strain was deliverable
NO local provider, importation bureaucratic problems
no provider who can supply
no reply to mails ,...
No response to emails
no strains available
no traceable contact person of collection of Russian Academy of Sciences
no worldwide databases available
nonexistent resources
Normally problems are with emerging pathogens

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Not all databases are easily accessible through the web.
not all resources are commercially available and working at a reference level requires access to unusual biomatter
Not always are available in the format you need
Not always info to find
Not disponible in Spain in some cases.
Not easy to find by Google
Not many people working in the same subject
not well documented
Occasionally it has been difficult to source a strain that has not been deposited in a culture collection
occasional problem
Often difficulty in finding who has what culture, particularly with different identifiers for the same strain from different collections.
Often very specific strains needed, with little information available
old published data
old strains sometimes difficult to track, as are those not deposited in culture collections
ometimes the strain(s) requested to Colleagues are not available due to different reasons
online resources are often incomplete
only for some specific strains
Organism apparently not in culture
original provider changed the lab, resources not properly stored and documented
people change their jobs
People move on
Plant introduction numbers are often published, it's not always clear from which gene bank and who identified those accessions
Problems obtaining antibiotic-producing non-type strains.
provider not always clearly identified or no longer traceable
Providers left an organisation and stocks were destroyed or misplaced
publications do not always specify the source of the strains used
rare resources
rare strains
references fro literature
Resource only available abroad in less known collection.
Resources lost.....
Resources only available from original research group which no longer exists or sent to licensed provider with no UK/European distributor
Some Archaea or anaerobes, mainly thermophiles are not easy to find where to be obtained
Some collections do not have their own Internet resources
Some culture collections are not easy to contact
Some isolates such as recent multi-resistant clinical isolates and very difficult to source (we use NARSA and BEI_
Some lab groups ended their activities and nobody is taking care of the collection
some microbial isolates are not available although described
Some microorganisms are difficult to find and an international list of providers is not available
some microorganisms are only in few Culture Collections around the world
Some microorganisms not provided by MRC
Some of the strains are not available in a strain collection
Some people have retired and their culture collections are either defunct or moved to new laboratories.
Some resources were only available in Asia.
some strains are difficult to find
Some strains are held in only one culture collection
Some strains are not easily available
Some strains or plasmids are heavily used in the literature but not available from the original lab, because they are old, or they are different from different labs and there is not a reference strain deposited in a public repository

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Some unique strains in culture collections had died out
Sometimes
Sometimes difficult to track who has a particular strain or plasmid.
Sometimes is not clear to whom is necessary to address to
Sometimes it takes me too much time to find the appropriate provider for an specific microorganisms
sometimes the same microorganism has different recognition codes in different collections
sometimes tools are not available any more in the lab from where they have been published
specific strains were no more available
Strain histories are sometimes difficult to ascertain from publications and information provided.
Strain published in a paper, but author or research group cannot be contacted
strain that I needed was no more accesible in culture collection
Strains described in papers not available from any culture collection.
strains got lodt because they were not deposited in collection
Strains in publications that can't be found in collections - need better details of genotype in publications so that equivalent strains can be found.
Strains no longer viable
strains not available from the supplier
strains not deposited in culture collections
Strains of <i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i> subsp. <i>insidiosus</i> , <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i> , <i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>actinidiae</i>
strains of filamentous fungi whose genome were sequenced, not always easy to find
That was in the case of bacteria described in papers with different codes
The first author moved on - and nobody reponds
The microorganism needed was sold only by one provider
the number provider is limited for private company at reaseanble price, liliting the number of strain available
There are not many 'easy" sources to find
there is no a single data base where all the resources can be check at once
This happens.
this problem is related with the above subject, some scientist give erroneous provider
This was for a particular strain of fungal strain and only one source was found to provide it.
type strains not available in culture collections for many anoxygenic phototrophic bacteria. also sometimes they do not revive from lyophilised vials. also even when active cultures are sent, they do not grow in our lab.
Unable to track-down published strains from studies 10-15 years ago
unclear depositing
Unclear rules at the destination
Very specific strains can be hard to find for example <i>Salmonella</i> strains for validation
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i> non "El Tor" not provided by Culture Collection, References lab was found and provide
We need in more information in on-line catalogues
when a biological resource is protected by a patent
where to look

7. Lack of documented properties of the resources

a frequent problem: traceability is difficult
absence of key data: biotope, date of isolation, origin country
As stated - limited documentation on the resource.
Bacterial lines naming and renaming needs centralisation! Loss of virulence information
Biochemical characterization was missing
carencia di informazioni
Co-resistances

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

culture conditions, no homogenization fo the nomenclature
depending on the sender
Difficulties in explaining tu custom authorities the nature of the material
difficulties in tracking current address of scientists describing microbial strains
Difficulties to find the original source of isolation of one type strain
difficulty in finding the appropriate resource
Documents not written in English
E.coli able to survive in fruit juices not found in Europe
especially , when the cultures were isolated prior 1990s
especially the characteristics of the microbes
Even ther country or host substrate of some strains in collections is not certainly known
Far too little documentation on culture collection sites PLUS search engines on most sites are difficult to use
for certain bacterial strains there is no proper info (proof of evidence) to link in to the particular strain!
For Mycobacterium tuberculosis from some collection
for very old resources this can be a porblem
Frequently
frequently
genetic properties poorly described, virulence capacity not always mentioned
genomic data, phenotypic data and alternative names for organisms/ strains often lacking
geographic, ecological information unavailable
importation rules based on known species, so unidentified treated as worst case
in case of DNA, sequence data is not provided
incorrect documentation of properties (e.g. plasmid map incorrect).
Info are often lacking
Information about specific requirements of the strains
Information can be lost as resources pass between users
iNFORMATION LACKING ON NATURE OF SAMPLES TAKEN DURING SURVEYS
Information not updated in the provider (culture collection) web page
insufficient characterization of samples
isolates not characterized thoroughly (for lack of time, money and/or importance)
It is not just lack of documentation--in many cases the published data are incorrect.
It would be very useful a more wide information about results obtained with strains relating to their biochemical properties. I mean it would be useful to obtain a sort of "Certificate of Analysis" including criteria, results, used methods. It would be useful to know the SOP followed for the Collection to check each strain
lack of all the information related to a specific bacteria
lack of detailed information
Lack of information about gene sequences and plasmids characteristics; need to buy a product to use a plasmid
Lack of information about origin of bacterial strains.
Lack of plasmid maps; lack of phenotypic characteristics of microorganisms or plasmids
Lack of publication of isolation data/experiments and failure to deposit in a culture collection
Limited background information on origin, properties and methods used
limited information on sampling
Mainly concerning old information
many strains have several names, most usually no more accessible
Material from old lab-collections where the person(s) that isolated the cultures are no longer available and documentation is no longer tracable
Materials from researchers frequently sent with little or no information and need to trawl through past publications to find properties
materiel and method not clear and corresponding author not helpful
minimal information received from collaborators
Most of the microorganisms applied in food industry are NN regarding their origin

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

no detailed information on the cultures published, e.g. in sequence databases
No details on isolation source, growth requirements, potential pathogenicity, how identification was done
No standard for documentet properties
non-cited properties in literature
not all data concerning isolates performed in our institution are accompanied by the background information where they originate
Not all individual scientists have proper documentation of the isolation procedure.
Not allways we have enoguh information about the source of the pathogen (culture, area, race)
Not everyone takes down and documents good information...sometimes it is very scant
Not everything is fully characterised or information was not easy to find on growth conditions, particularly when we needed minimal medium
not really a problem. Nobody ever spoke about it
not usually a problem but, there is always room for improvement
not well documented
occasionally
often and that is a no go for us
often very little data
online resources are often incomplete
origin and properties of cell lines and microbial culture is sometime poorly described on websites
origin of strains is not always well documented
Origin of the isolates (date of isolation, sampling site, underlying disease if any)
original sources of materials remain often undefined
Partial plasmid maps, lack of info on resistance genes
phenotype and genomic marker are not always cleary noted
plasmids without correct maps/sequence
Problems with culture media specified
Properties in which we are intrested not always clearly defined or researched
Scarce information regarding resucitation and conservation of strains
Secondary metabolites are often not listed in strain descriptions.(This is not related to CBD)
See answer to "biosecurity rules"
Some documentation belongs to scientific papers which requires high level of experience and knowledge to be completely understood.
some information sources do not have clear information
Some isolates are so old that there are not good descriptions, little sequence data, etc.
Some obtained resources have had incomplete metadata associated with them, for historical reasons
Some properties, which were important, were not described.
some resources are meagerly described, just the bare minimum
Some strains have not been fully characterized, or the information is difficult to find.
Sometimes
sometimes culture conditions are not enough specified and bacteria is difficult or impossible to grow
Sometimes difficult to get the details/sequence of some plasmids.
sometimes happens
Sometimes is not clear to whom is necessary to adress to
Sometimes lack karyotype or EBV status for human cancer lines.
specific strains were no more available
Strain ID can be wrong
strains arrived with no propoer information to be culture sucesfully
strains do not have the properties they should have
Strains from other research labs do not always have specific provenance.
strains in CC whith fragmentary documents, responsible scientists left the institution
Strains not corresponding to the supposed material deposited
The assays used to characterize a cell lineage were not enough sufficient

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

the strain obtained from the original isolator had not been fully characterised metabolically (though published)
too scarce information to know growth conditions
unclear depositing
unknown hosts of plant pathogenic bacteria
Unpublished results
when study of functionality between an isolated strain and another strain of the same species purchased in a Culture Collection

8. Other problems

Cell lines sent by researchers frequently mycoplasma contaminated or wrong STR profiles
communication and organisation of the transport etc
Complicate to transfer material to other collaborator after getting cultures, transfer permit complicated
culture conditions
culturing pure strains
custom regulations
customs officials not always understanding regulations pertaining to biological substance transport
Delay in the deliver of requested resources for a long time (even one year)
Difficulty to accomplish international transactions
Has been impossible to resuscitate some strains; too many misidentified strains in culture collections
Infectiosity of material
Lack of growth of the strain, certificate of the strain not complete
lack of reference material
lack of typification information and references
legal permissions of politic authorities
Mexican authorities require a special permit to import biological material and othes substances and it is dificult to obtain
misidentification of strains
Misidentified strains deposited in culture collection.
Mislabelled strains in the collections
Nécessité de LOA et laboratoire sous agrément 2008 61 CE
obtain high concentration of some microorganism
often the material has been discarded!!!!
One, the Culture Collection sent to us a different bacteria (at the species level) that the one we ordered, this caused a big problem in our laboratory because we used it as reference.
Patented resource
price expensive for dna or strain, delay.
Problems to contact authorities in the country of origin
Quality issues can be a problem
Significant delays because of shipping in normal mail overseas.
Some Culture Collection have not been able to grow some microorganisms that other CC has done without difficulties.
The culture buy did not grow.
Uncertainty over permission to import environmental samples for culture studies outside the country of origin when the fungi have not been identified
We have had very few problems with European collections THANKS

6.6.6. Q23 Do you have additional comments to share about the origin of microbial/genetic resources that your Laboratory unit uses and/or legal issues related to the CBD ?

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

A major problem is sourcing recent clinical isolates that are free to use. When developing new drugs or looking at mechanisms of resistance RECENT and APPROPRIATE isolates are needed
Apologies, I only know of the excellent service provided by CABI
CBD, we have just read about it
Cell bank resources expensive to obtain when research funding is limited so informal network of supply is essential
For valid publication of isolated bacteria, it is required to deposit the strain that can be released to anyone in two culture collections (different countries). In case of a patented strain, it can not be published in IJSEM. Although it is patented, the strain can be distributed to anyone for research purpose (not for commercial) by signing agreement. Therefore, the limitation of this needs to be amended to excavate and publicise more valuable microorganisms.
Having problem to deposit cultures isolated from sample collected at a country where MOI has not yet made between Japan.
I had most problems sending the material to other countries such as USA or China
I recommend all resources should be free.
I think that there should be fatty acid profiles or some other markers available for each strain the strain bank offers, to guarantee that this is the strain one looks for because literature references are not adequate. Also, names of bacteria frequently change which makes it even more difficult to search for the proper strain.
In general, far too much bureaucracy: too many details to be provided etc Interpretation of the CBD is very country specific. Some countries are reasonable and want to facilitate utilization of their genetic resources; others are very restrictive. At early stages legal costs can quickly derail negotiations. Countries need to be open at first (just establish ownership), details of compensation should be delayed till what is discovered is known. [New drug class BIG; biopesticide small]
It would be helpful if the EU would find common rules and clear, simple procedures regulating the access to genetic resources.
Keep in mind the way the US ATCC is set up is absolutely not the way to proceed! They are a mess for small companies like us!
Most of the microbial resources used in the Laboratory unit are isolated by ourselves within the country, so that we do not have so many problems in exchanges
need some information about it.
Not only the 3rd world countries should protect their resources.
Please don't make it any more difficult as more will be discarded.
Some situations we have found a lack of harmonisation between countries
The convention is too restrictive.
The country's 2008 CBD-related report does NOT include any information on yeasts and fungi, their biodiversity status or dangers from imported human, animal or plant pathogens. There is only one reference to microbial biodiversity issues in the whole of that report without a critical appraisal of the issues that could have been raised by the country's Collections. This remains the only report since 2008.
The current regulations have restricted investigative work on the world fungal resource, to the detriment of both countries of origin and those importing them, and further restrict critical molecular-phylogenetic studies. I consider that the current CBD, and national legislation built on that framework, has brought no or little benefit to less-developed countries and been counter-productive. It is constraining fundamental and applied research, and for microbial groups at least would be better replaced by a Code of Conduct developed by UNEP in collaboration with FAO, WHO, IUMS and/or the WFCC.
the ownership and dissemination of strains isolated in partnership is poorly addressed which paves the way 'backdoor' practices
the wrong material had been sent more than once causing months of delay in the research in progress
We are not aware of CBD and I consider it as an intrusion. If I want to study any bacteria from any biotope, why ask any permission ???
We have so far only been working with GRAS type microbes
When I stored an isolate with MRC I would have an opportunity to get the microorganisms free of charge for my future study.

6.6.7. Q24 Indicate which services you ordered from Culture collections in the past five years, and which ones you intend to order from Culture collections in the next five years.

Chemical analysis of bacterial Wall compounds
Data relating to holdings, their provenance and phenotypic details, etc.
Purified bacterial DNA
Buying lyophilized strains: Ordered in the past five years and Intend to order in the next five years
As we are a culture collections I can obtain these in house if needed.
we take use other microbial laboratory's

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

I do not fully understand "Culture Collections". For sequencing we usually order the service to companies that are not Culture Collections, and the same for other entries
DNA base composition Quinone analysis
cell sorting for single cell genomes
You cannot ask like this, isn't it all usually a question of the price. If the collection would offer a great price, there's be all sorts of interes
Menaquinone analysis.
DNA content, Analysis of quinones, polar lipids, mycolic acid, peptidoglycan, cell wall sugars
Purchase of bacterial strains
EBV immortalisation of lymphocytes

6.6.8. Q26 In case you have indicated 'because of gaps' for any of the services in the previous question, describe these gaps in a few words in the corresponding textbox(es).

not aware of all services offered by collection cultures
Partial characterization of biological material
not all organisms are always present in available culture collections.
A Culture Collection has lost a strain
In the table above, I misses a column indicating that services were provided by a company/organisation different to Culture Collections
often missing

6.6.9. Q27 In case you have indicated "because of other shortcomings' for any of the services, describe these shortcomings in a few words in the corresponding textbox(es).

1. Price

All procedures marked are too expensive.
As university, some services are too expensive to use.
Attending training courses in Europ is expensive, funding not always available
cheaper outside
depends on our budget i.e. sequestration
difference in prices between Poland and euro (or dolar) zone is so big that most off offered services is too expensive for our lab
expensive
Generally the services offered by culture collections for fatty acid analyses, polar lipids etc are very expensive. The market for DNA sequence generation and analysis is very competitive and as culture collections are currently operated I would be surprised if they could compete on price.
genomic DNA: too expensive, yield not guaranteed
high
high cost
Higher prices than closer available places
it is sometimes a problem
less expensive
Limited financial resources
low funds for analyses
mainly
NO HA SIDO CONSULTADO EN NINGUNA OCASIÓN
Often an issue.
operating on a very limited budget; would like to outsource more, if I could afford the expenses

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

Our scale of research funding is low
price
sometimes too high
the institution has no enough budget
the price of the analyses may be shortcoming factor for the pre-experiments
There were no funds available for these services
Too expensive
Usually more expensive
VERY HIGH
We are budgetary unit.

2. Time Frame

Always an issue.
LONG
sometimes these services are very slow, in particular when cell lines are ordered from Great Britain (up to 6 months) or mouse embryos from US (6-12 months)
sometimes
Time lag is longer than when using local companies
we already know other providers, then it is faster

3. Administrative burden

Customs declaration for cell lines in fetal calf serum, import of frozen mouse embryos, no help to deal with customs problems
it is also a problem
More difficulties in shipping the samples out in good condition, and coordinating with vendor
sometimes
unknown specification of services
VERY LONG AND TROUBLE

4. Other

Collaboration with private societies from France or other countries
difficulties in sending the cultures due to custom regulations
for sequencing, we ordered to local based facilities
in many cases we are at the origin of annotations; for other cases we (perhaps wrongly) think that available services exist elsewhere
in-person courses (if its possible, I prefer online course)
internal budget constraints
LIMITACIONES DERIVADAS DE LA DOTACIÓN INSTRUMENTAL DEL LABORATORIO
método de estandarización complicado
not possible to get payment docs in Russian
Shipping complications
some analyses are done in cooperation with other institutes
We order DNA and RNA sequencing from specialized companies, not from collections. Please, work to eliminate the use of DNA-DNA hybridization; it is an obsolete technique and the major problem to advance the taxonomy and classification of bacteria.
We use other private labs services to do it

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

6.6.10. Q28 In case you would use the training service in the next five years, what kind of training program(s) would be useful for your laboratory unit?

Pathogenicity tests
Microbial pathogenicity test
Access to data relating to resources held.
Because it is necessary for patent purposes
I was asked to ask for instructions on culture
Whole genome sequencing
specific techniques or bioinformatics
Our culture collection offers training so not strictly relevant
None. We can handle it by ourself.
Continuous updating in management of Culture Collection resources and the pertinent legal aspects.
data analysis: specifically raw data from pyrosequencing

6.6.11. Q29 On which subjects do you expect to receive information from the Culture Collections, with respect to the biological material offer?

In case of quantified materials, certificate of analysis (validation certificate), analysis conditions and expected results: average quantity, dispersion limits intervals etc
Related microbes.
Related strains
If there is a description published, then much of the information I need should be in that. Such references are often linked on culture collection web pages, making it easy to obtain. However, some journals are not open access, in which case it would be useful if the culture collection provided that information, even if in a summary form.
It is very important in the history, to have details of how fungi were isolated and the number of subcultures done until it reaches the user. These procedures may affect fungi in terms of the DNA sequences for example.
synonyms
Chemotaxonomic characteristics such as quinone system
MADLT-TOF fingerprinting data
potential contamination, known problems / issues (e.g. retracted publications relating to the microorganism)
Secondary metabolites
preservation conditions
S1, S2, S3, S4 classification according to different countries' legislations

6.6.12. Q31 In case the culture collection presents information on its biological material online, which tools would you like to see implemented ?

Well described stable programmatic interfaces, standardised across collections.
search tool that uses all possible fields per record
make links to other relevant databases
semantic information
Whichever is most convenient for the Collection
PDF data sheet for offline use
Very important to allow local processing of data.

Annex 6: Overview comments or other responses per question

6.6.13. Q32 What kind of information, linking the phenotype of the biological material to its genotype, is of relevance for your work?

Generally, connections to molecular data are critical for us as a molecular data services and research institute.
Not relevant for us
Links to 16S or 18S rRNA databases for taxonomic purposes
morphology, biochemical
SE NECESITARÁN EN LOS PRÓXIMOS 5 AÑOS
Links to SNP databases
As mentioned the history of the isolates are crucial. So how it was isolated, preserved and subcultured.
pubmed
Gideon Database
genetic or other profiles for cell identity
Taxonomy databases Litterature databases
Links to expression analyses eg GEO
Links to literature describing any such linkages described by depositors